

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D1.4 Annual Summary Report (ASR) Y1 Reporting period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 Second version

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Technical References

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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	21/10/2022	GB members	
2	23/11/2022	GSB members	
3	20/02/2023	PARC Coordination Team and MB members	Clarifications given in the first version of the ASR submitted on 05/01/2023, based on the comments received from HaDEA

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List of abbreviations

3R: Reduction, Refinement and Replacement	KEs: Key Events
ADME: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion	KPI: Key Performance Indicator
AE: Affiliated Entity	MB: Management Board
AI: Artificial Intelligence	ML: Machine Learning
ANT : Acute NeuroToxicity	MCRA: Monte Carlo Risk Assessment
AO/ AON/ AOP: Adverse Outcome/ AO Network/ Pathway	LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
API: Application Programming Interfaces	MoA: Mode of Action
ASR/ AWP: Annual Summary Report/Work Plans	MIEs: Molecular Initiating Events
CA: Consortium Agreement	MS: Member States
CL/ ML: Chemical Leader/ Methodology Leader	NAMs: New Approach Methodologies
CLP: Classification, Labelling and Packaging	NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment
CMS: Content Management System	NHs: National Hubs
COPCSD: Common Open Platform on Chemical Safety Data	NR: Nuclear Receptor
CSS: Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability	NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points
CT: ANSES PARC Coordination Team	NGTxC : Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens
DEPB: Data and Ethics Protection Board	NTS: Non-Targeted Screening
DMP: Data Management Plan	OECD: Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
DNT : Developmental NeuroToxicity	OO: Operational Objectives
DoA: Description of Action	PFAS: per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
EC: European Commission	PFDP: PARC FAIR Data Policy
ECHA: European Chemicals Agency	BPA: Bisphenol A
ED/ EDCs: Endocrine Disrupters / endocrine disrupting compounds	PBK: Physiologically Based Kinetic
EDA: Effect-Directed Analysis	PBTK: Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic
EFSA: European Food Safety Authority	PEC: Predicted Environmental Concentration
ERA: Environmental Risk Assessment	POD: Point of Departure
EUSES: European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances	PPP: Plant Protection Products
EWS: Early Warning System	PSIP: Partnership Specific Impact Pathways
FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	QA/QC: Quality Assurance / Quality Control
FIP: FAIR Implementation Profiles	QAWG: Quality Assurance Working Group
GA: Grant Agreement	QIVIVE: Quantitative in vitro / in vivo Extrapolation
GB: Governing Board	QSAR: Quantitative Structure Activity Relationship
GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation	RA/RM: Risk Assessment / Risk Management
GFF: GO FAIR Foundation	R&I: Research and Innovation
GIVIMP: Good In Vitro Methods Practices	RRM: Rapid Response Mechanism
GS: Grant Signatory	SDGs: Sustainable Development Goals
GSB: Grant Signatory Board	S2PD: Science-to-Policy Dialogue
HA: Hazard Assessment	SAICM: Strategic Approach to International Chemicals Management
HBM: Human BioMonitoring	SF: Stakeholder Forum
	SO: Specific Objectives

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<p>HBM GV: Health-based Guidance Values IATA: Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment IB: International Board IPM: Integrated Pest Management IPR: Intellectual Property Rights ISES: International Society of Exposure Science IVIVE: <i>in vitro</i> - <i>in vivo</i> extrapolation JRC: Joint Research Centre</p>	<p>SRIA: Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda SS: Suspect Screening SbD: Safe-by-Design SSbD: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design T/TL: Task/Task co-leaders THSD: Thyroid Hormone System Disruption THS: Thyroid Hormone System TTC: Toxicological Threshold of Concern UCWG: Use Case Working Group(s) UNEP: United Nations Environment Programme US-EPA: US Environmental Protection Agency US-NTP: US National Toxicology Program WHO: World Health Organization WP/ WPL: Work Package / WP co-leaders</p>
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Definitions

SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda):

For the Year 1 of PARC, SRIA is an annex of AWPY1 presenting a summary of the projects organized by WPs/Tasks/Activities. The term SRIA has been replaced from year 2 by PARC Project Portfolio.

From Year 2 of PARC, SRIA will be an overarching document presenting PARC at a strategic level with PARC vision, objectives, exit strategy, a description of what has been achieved and what will be done in the next year(s) organized by specific topics related to risk assessment (monitoring, hazard, environment, mixtures...). As Annexes to the SRIA, there will be a summary map of WPs and activities to understand the connections and a list of projects organized by specific topics. SRIA will be an additional deliverable attached to the GB meeting and then reported to the Commission every year.

PARC Project Portfolio: Annex of the AWP from AWPY2 presenting a summary of the projects organized by WPs/Tasks/Activities with a short description of WP/Task as an introduction.

Abstract

The Annual Summary Report (ASR) reflects the results of the work achieved during the calendar year. As the project started on 1 May 2022, the first ASR covers the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 (8 months).

Main achievements are briefly described below:

- WP1: An effective management and governance framework is set up and appropriate tools are provided. The monitoring framework is being discussed with the relevant actors to ensure it is adapted to the objectives and impacts of PARC. The Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) is in the process of being set-up and first ethics and data protection discussions are being initiated.

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- WP2: A process and criteria for project review and approval is validated and implemented for the projects included in the PARC rolling SRIA. Preliminary discussions and conceptual developments have been initiated for the development of NGRAroute and PARCopedia and task forces created to structure the future work. The framework for Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs) and their nomination is ongoing. A process for continuous dialogue with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) is implemented and a first survey to collect input on needs, capacity building and sustainability has been launched.
- WP3: The criteria for selection and a list of potential participants in the Stakeholder Forum and International Board are identified. The initial composition of the Stakeholder Forum (SF) and the International Board (IB) has been established. The graphical identity for PARC and a PARC website landing page is being created. The web development is initiated and the PARC communication and dissemination strategy is set. The rules for the establishment of official synergies between external projects and PARC are under development.
- WP4: For HBM, three working groups each focusing on one aspect of the work: i) review and update of materials; ii) areas of needs and improvements in PARC; iii) solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation, are set up. The Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) is created and the needs for QA and comparability of the HBM data generated are identified. Two projects linking exposure and health related information are initiated. A first inventory of existing prioritisation schemes, as a preparatory work for the development of a framework for automated assessment and prioritisation of chemicals / matrices / endpoints deserving attention for future monitoring projects is initiated. A pilot project on the monitoring of per-/polyfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) in the environment is launched. Six projects relating to the alignment of main concepts and strategical vision regarding innovative methods, definition and harmonisation of QA/QC issues for suspect screening/ Non-Targeted Screening/ (SS/NTS) approaches, relevant contribution to Early Warning System, elaboration of integrated Data Processing Workflow, as well as two first proof-of-concept applications focused on perinatal exposure and wastewater based epidemiology are launched.
- WP5: Groups of substances with data gaps on hazard for human health and environmental health that can be closed in PARC are selected for initial studies: these include natural toxins and Bisphenol A (BPA) alternatives. Endpoints to be tested are selected and projects defined and started. Projects related to the development of innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for non-genotoxicity carcinogenicity, metabolic disruption, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity, and developmental neurotoxicity have been initiated, as well as for environmental toxicology / ecotoxicology of BPA alternatives. A project on prioritised New Approach Methodologies (NAM)-based mechanistic hazard characterisation and translation to human pathophysiology is defined. A core group with expertise in methods for Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) development, three specialty groups immunotoxicity and Non-Genotoxic Carcinogens (NGTxC); endocrine disruption; neurotoxicity and an effect markers groups have started working on inventorying available methods and four different brainstorming groups within task 5.3 are established to develop a strategy for data recovery and development of case studies to

address knowledge as well as conceptual gaps *in vitro* to *in vivo* extrapolation Physiologically Based Kinetic (IVIVE-PBK) models.

- WP6: Four projects aimed at the development, testing and evaluation of Integrative Approaches for testing and Assessment (IATAs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity are launched. For the first round of IATA evaluation case studies, criteria and candidate substances are identified and discussions on how to best achieve incorporation of PBK modelling results are underway. For improving integrated risk assessment, two projects on aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes of exposure for the general population and workers are launched. The project are working on inventories of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population and the inventory of occupational and general life models to estimate exposure from various sources and routes of exposure. Two projects on the refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment and mixtures risk assessment have started. Initial work is launched on a strategy to perform risk assessment of mixtures organised into 3 groups of experts working on (integration of exposure data, hazard assessment and grouping chemicals into mixture assessment groups and kinetics to bridge risk assessment based on HBM data with external exposure assessment as performed by the European Agencies). Two approaches for the identification of exposure to mixtures in real-life based on human biomonitoring observations are explored to better understand co-exposure to chemicals with the same health impact. Four projects on human health impact assessment and risk indicators have been started. Case studies reviewing substance-specific Risk Assessment (RA) depending on intended use and case studies reviewing effect-specific RA are initiated, as well as a project reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA. Two projects and scoping activities are launched to contribute to the development of regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures and three to facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods. Initial landscaping exercises have been carried out for the evaluation of information on substances in products and materials and how it can be integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments. Concerning ecological risk assessment to protect biodiversity, five projects are defined and initiated.
- WP7: The development of an integrated approach to training in FAIRification according to the three-point FAIRification framework (3PFF) and support to the WP in development of conceptual models, vocabularies and ontologies has been initiated. The PARC initial Data Management Plan is set. Data Champions and Data Liaisons, and the FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) are established and training has started. Cross-work package working group on vocabularies & ontologies is established and collaborative workflows are available both for the onboarding of new PARC projects into the FAIR processes and for the triage and identification of FAIR Data Use Cases. Inventory of major databases, repositories and other relevant sources for chemical risk assessment is underway. Discussions on PARC-relevant domain-level FAIR implementation profiles (FIP) are initiated. The first year's data use cases on human biomonitoring datasets, monitoring PFAS and endocrine disruptors and databases of chemicals in articles enable the identification of core data hub services and the gaps to be filled. A list of inventories of different statistical approaches and computational tools suitable for / used in meta- and pooled analysis is available as well as a workflow for meta-analysis task and the use cases for the scoping review on the integration and analysis of (heterogeneous) FAIR data and scoping study on uncertainty analysis are identified.

- WP8: An inventory and review of existing tools that are currently available from existing initiatives on Safe-by-Design (SbD) (nano) and Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) has been carried out and user requirements and functional specifications of the PARC SSbD toolbox are mapped out. The optimal set of parameters for selecting potential use cases to test the methodology developed by the EC and complement the use cases chosen by the EC are identified and a set of potential case studies formulated. Standardised protocols for early warning monitoring tools are under development, with a particular focus on suspect/non-targeted/Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA)-based tools, as well as methods in line with NAMs. A literature analysis of existing Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems in Early Warning Systems (EWS) and the summarising overview in the context of their reliability and usefulness for chemicals prioritisation regarding toxicity is ongoing. A selection of databases with chemical structure and identifier information has been carried out and a review of existing studies for the identification of possible case studies that can be used for establishment of early warning monitoring tools and prioritisation framework for humans, environment, and products is ongoing. Concerning integrative models, an inventory of existing front-end access platforms and a critical review from the user-perspective is carried out. A case study on bisphenols (BPA and alternatives) has been selected as an initial set of use cases. A first draft of an overarching conceptual model that maps models and platforms to user requirements and RA questions is developed.
- WP9: Networks of contact points for laboratory and exposure monitoring networking is established. An online survey to gather information for the catalogues on laboratory and infrastructure expertise, availability and capacities in the different fields has been elaborated. Working groups for harmonising Quality Assurance (QA)/Quality Control (QC) protocols/guidance for sampling, for chemical analysis, and in toxicity testing and toxicokinetics are established and first alignment within WP4 and 5 is implemented. An online survey to gather information on initial training needs is developed and was sent to the National Hubs Contact Points NHCPs.

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Authors and Acknowledgments

The results and outputs listed in this report were carried out and produced in a joint effort of all participants of the PARC consortium. In this report it is not foreseen to explicitly name all participants who have contributed to the described activities and outputs. More detailed information about which participant contributed to which task will be detailed in the future Periodic Technical Reports.

Objectives

The Partnership is set up to consolidate and strengthen European public R&I capacities in chemical Risk Assessment (RA) to protect human health and the environment and has an objective-oriented structure to answer the end-users' needs. Linked to this general objective are three specific objectives (SO) around which the nine Work Packages (WP) of PARC are structured and for which 13 realistic, measurable, achievable and verifiable operational objectives (OO) are developed.

Specific PARC objectives are:

Specific objective 1:

- Set up an EU-wide sustainable cross-disciplinary network to identify and agree on research and innovation needs and to support research uptake into regulatory chemical risk assessment.

Specific objective 2:

- Set up joint EU research and innovation activities responding to identified priorities in support of current regulatory risk assessment processes for chemical substances and to emerging challenges.

Specific objective 3:

- Strengthening existing capacities and building new transdisciplinary platforms to support chemical risk assessment.

The Partnership brings together Ministries and national public health and risk assessment agencies, as well as research organisations and academia from almost all of EU Member States. Representatives of Directorates-General of the EC and EU agencies involved in the monitoring of chemicals and the assessment of risks are also participating. PARC will meet the needs of risk assessment agencies to better anticipate emerging risks and respond to the challenges and priorities of the new European policies.

Participants are currently working towards the objectives set for each task in the Annual Work Plan 2022.

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1. Explanation of the work carried out per WP

1.1. Work package 1. Coordination and management

1.1.1. Task 1.1. Overall executive management and support of the Partnership

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Participants: All GSB members and WP co-leaders

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Setting up an effective management and governance framework for the PARC consortium in compliance with the legal, ethical, financial and administrative rules and regulations and ensuring the highest quality standards.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ PARC launch and implementation of the Consortium Governance Bodies and their procedures

- PARC started on 1st of May 2022 and successful launch events, organised by the PARC Coordination Team (CT), took place during the period 11-13 May 2022, notably the kick-off meeting on 12-13 May 2022, at the Cité des Sciences, in Paris, France, which brought together over 220 participants onsite and over 340 online. The first physical meeting of the PARC Management Board (MB) and of the PARC Governing Board (GB) took place ahead on 11 May 2022 at ANSES Headquarters. Additionally, the PARC CT organised monthly virtual MB meetings from June 2022 to December 2022 (7 in total). For all these meetings, minutes have been made available on the PARC Consortium SharePoint.

-The PARC consortium governance and management bodies and their roles were established by M6 by the PARC CT, in collaboration with the relevant parties, as expected (MS2): the GB Terms of reference were adopted by the GB during its first meeting and the PARC Consortium Agreement was finalised in May 2022 and signed by the 37 PARC Beneficiaries, and 23 Associated Partners. Also, the PARC governance process timeline (D1.2) was defined and the network of NHCP and functioning rules (MS3) was established. However, the official nomination of the MLs/CLs is delayed and planned in Spring 2023. It was initially foreseen to consider the substances identified in the joint prioritization round HBM4EU and PARC but the number of chemicals in the final list was very high and we came to the conclusion that some of them were not being addressed in PARC. As such it was necessary to identify the chemicals and the methodologies being address in PARC and this takes longer than initially foreseen.

➤ Set up of the tools and structure for the day-to-day management and close follow-up of the Partnership activities

The PARC CT set up an internal communication platform (PARC Consortium SharePoint) to provide shared access to internal working documents with the consortium:

- The PARC Handbook describing the internal requirements and specifying the common rules to be followed by all PARC Participants. It is a living document, which will evolve throughout the implementation of PARC.
- Templates and tools for the monitoring and reporting of PARC, such as templates for the preparation of the ASR and AWP, templates for the description of the projects, templates for deliverables and milestones, templates for Decision Memo etc.

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- A maintained up-to-date contacts list of the different PARC boards (GB, GSB, MB, and NHCPs) and of the consortium (Beneficiaries and Affiliated Entities and Associated Partners).
- The PARC CT set up restricted libraries for document sharing within the PARC Consortium boards and Hub contact points for the different PARC management bodies (GB, GSB, MB and NHCPs).
- The PARC CT assisted PARC participants on specific administrative and financial questions related to the implementation.

➤ Financial issues and setting up of the tools and structure for the close follow-up of the Partnership budget

- The EU pre-financing received by ANSES was distributed to the Beneficiaries according to the internal rules set up in the Consortium Agreement.
- The PARC CT developed financial templates for the collect of the budget for transversal activities and projects and set up an information system (EMDESK) for the monitoring of the implementation of the PARC workplan (WP, tasks, activities and projects) and the use of resources (PMs and costs) all along the Partnership's lifetime.

➤ Contractual documents generated by PARC activities

- The PARC CT is implementing a collaboration agreement with JRC, as well as confidentiality agreements with Scientific Advisory Groups or external experts developed under the scientific WPs.

➤ Communication

- The PARC CT set up internal and external communication rules, in collaboration with WP3, which are detailed in the PARC Handbook and in the deliverable D3.2 Communication and dissemination strategy.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D1.2	PARC governance process timeline	ANSES	31/05/2022 (M1)	12/07/2022 (M3)	PARC governance process timeline: 2 months delay due to additional discussions and clarifications with the European Commission on the expectations regarding the ASR and AWP and their date of submission
MS2	Governance and management bodies and roles are established	ANSES	31/10/2022 (M6)	Ongoing	CA signed by all beneficiaries, Terms of reference are adopted for the GB, but ML/CL are not yet nominated (Spring 2023)
MS3	Establishment of the network of NHCP and functioning rules	ANSES	31/10/2022 (M6)	14/11/2022 (M7) (achieved after validation by the MB)	No significant delay
MS7	Establishment of working groups	ANSES	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.1.2. Task 1.2. Scientific steering and implementation of Annual Work Plans

Leader: ANSES (FR)

Participants: All WP co-leaders, NHCPs, NHCs, DOMG (BE), INSA (PT), NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Setting up the tools to ensure the Partnership's progress and guiding the PARC consortium and its activities in maintaining the course set out in the DoA, to achieve milestones and produce the agreed deliverables, within the defined budget and abiding by the highest quality standards.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

- Preparation and submission of AWP Y1 and Y2 with the SRIA in Annex and ASRY1
 - The PARC CT submitted the first AWP and the PARC rolling SRIA in Annex in June 2022 (D1.1). Further to revisions by the PARC MB, task co-leaders and participants, a revised version of the D1.1 was submitted in October 2022 to HADEA.
 - The AWP for Year 2 and updated PARC rolling SRIA (D1.3) prepared by the PARC CT, the MB in collaboration with the Task co-leaders and the PARC Participants, will be submitted before the end of January 2023. D1.3 integrates 60 projects in implementation phase for the year one and 5 projects in initiation phase for the year 2 (it has to be noted that one new project has been included as a new case study, part of the WP6 project P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU of Year 1). For each project, it provides information on the objectives, main expected outputs, outcomes and impacts, links within and outside PARC, contribution to key PARC Deliverables and Milestones, involved partners, the schedule and an estimation of the costs.
 - The ASRY1 was prepared by the PARC CT, the MB in collaboration with the Task co-leaders and the PARC Participants (D1.4) and a first version was submitted on 5 January 2022.
 - Virtual meetings of the GB and the GSB were organised on 21 November and 13 December 2022 respectively to discuss and validate the content of the first ASR and second AWP. Another meeting of the GSB will be organised end of January 2023 in order to present the budget for the year 2 of PARC before we submit the AWPY2.
- Follow-up of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones
 - The PARC CT set up a review process, validated by the MB, for deliverables, additional deliverables and key deliverables (key deliverables correspond to those that are of special interest for the GB and will then be reviewed by GB members before submission to the EC).
 - The PARC CT ensured the submission of the deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones due during the year 1 of PARC to the European Commission with the required justification in case of delay.
- Amendments to the Grant Agreement
 - The PARC CT collected the requests for changes received from the PARC Participants that will be integrated in the next amendment of the PARC Grant Agreement (GA). EC initiated an amendment to update Annex 5 of the GA and included changes in the reporting periods to 18, 18, 18, 18, and 12 M

and cancelled two Annual Summary Reports (ASR Y2 and ASR Y6). The summary of the activities for those years will be included in the public summary of the periodic report.

➤ Assistance to the PARC NHCs in defining the National Hub (NH) contributions and activities in PARC

- The PARC CT helped the PARC National Hub Coordinators (NHC) in setting up the network of National Hub Contacts Points (NHCP) and functioning rules of the National Hubs (MS3 submitted in October 2022).

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D1.1	AWP Y1 including rolling SRIA	ANSES	31/05/2022 (M1)	10/06/2022 (M2)	The first version of the deliverable was submitted in June 2022. Following the comments received from the European Commission, the PARC CT updated the AWP Y1 and the annex SRIA of the AWP Y1 and the revised D1.1 has been submitted in October 2022 to the European Commission.
D1.3	AWP Y2 including rolling SRIA	ANSES	31/12/2022 (M8)	27/01/2023 (M9)	The first version of the AWP Y2 has been submitted to HADEA in January 2023 with the technical description of the work planned for the Y2 of PARC. A complete version of the AWP Y2 with the validated budgetary information will be submitted to HADEA in February 2023
D1.4	ASR Y1	ANSES	31/12/2022 (M8)	05/01/2023 (M9)	The first version of the deliverable was submitted in January 2023. Following the comments received from the European Commission, the PARC CT updated the ASR Y1 and the revised D1.4 will be submitted to HADEA in February 2023

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.1.3. Task 1.3. Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership

Leader: DOMG (BE), INSA (PT)

Participants: All WP co-leaders

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Setting up the monitoring framework for the Partnership

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

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- The feedback of the EC’s expert group on Partnership monitoring frames to fine-tune the list of indicators was received and the PARC Partnership Specific Impact Pathways PSIPs and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were included in the Biennial Monitoring Report 2022 on Partnerships under Horizon Europe’.
- DOMG and ANSES participated in the panel discussion as representative of a co-funded partnership in the Hearing of Partnerships Representatives on the Partnerships Knowledge Hub’s opinion on the Biennial Monitoring Report 2022 on Partnerships under Horizon Europe.
- On the 13th of September a task meeting was held to discuss the further development of the first set of indicators and planning of work in line with the work planned for Y1 (DOMG – INSA – ANSES).
- Follow up meetings on the revision of the 1st list have been held between DOMG and VITO (27/09) the DOMG-VITO-INSA (19/10) and a virtual task 1.3 meeting was held on the 10th of November to decide on a revised draft list of indicators that will be sent to different PARC bodies for consultation.
- First interactions with WP2 – task 2.2 on sustainability and with WP3 – on communication aspects (e.g. the use and possible integration of indicator leaflets on the website) have taken place and specific meetings are planned to discuss relevant indicators for WP2/WP3.
- A realistic strategy and timeline for consultation of different PARC bodies was set up and discussed at the September task 1.3 meeting. This should allow to come with a revised list of indicators (D1.6) by April 2023, as planned.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS6	Revised monitoring frame	DOMG/INSA	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
D1.6	Optimised list of indicators	DOMG/INSA	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.1.4. Task 1.4. Ethics framework

Leader: NIJZ (SI), EHESP (FR)

Participants: All WP co-leaders

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Setting up the Data and Ethics Protection Board (DEPB) and discussing ethics and data protection with the other WP co-leaders in order to set the ethics framework for the Partnership

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

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- The Deliverable D10.2 Ethic Assessment report for Year 1 (OEI - Requirement No. 2) has been submitted to the EC in June 2022. The D10.2 focuses on ethics issues related to the activities that will be implemented during the first year of PARC.
- The Data and Ethic Protection Board (DEPB) is expected to be established by the beginning of 2023. The DEPB should be composed of two external experts and three representatives from the research and data-centric WPs of the partnership (WP4, WP5, and WP7).
- To smoothen up the communication and implementation of data and ethics processes, all WPs have nominated an Ethics contact point. In addition, and in collaboration with WP7, Data contacts points have similarly been identified.
- The Ethics Charter initiated by the PARC CT and Task 1.4 co-leaders has been prepared and disseminated amongst PARC participants. This document is intended to be a code of conduct, which highlight good practices and recommendations that should be followed by PARC participants to reduce and/or address ethical issues that may arise during the Partnership implementation.
- The MB members have filled in and will maintain a Declaration of Interest annually.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D10.2	OEI - Requirement No. 2	ANSES	31/05/2022 (M1)	13/07/2022 (M3)	No significant delay
MS1	Establishment of Data and Ethics Protection	NIJZ/E HESP	31/10/2022 (M6)	Ongoing	Delayed Composition of the DEPB (the members of the DEPB will be selected by mid-February)
D10.1	OEI - Requirement No. 1	ANSES	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	The members of the DEPB will be selected by mid-February and the report will be prepared consequently
D10.3	OEI - Requirement No. 3	ANSES	31/12/2022 (M8)	Ongoing	Expected to be submitted by mid-February 2023 with the AWPY2. The PARC CT is collecting ethics information from the task co-leaders and project leaders to prepare the deliverable
D1.5	Ethics and data protection policy	NIJZ/E HESP	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected at this stage, it will depend on the time of implementation of the board and how the interactions are made with WP7.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

The deadline for candidates to submit their application for the DEPB has to be expanded as there were not enough candidates after the first round. Interviews will be organised in January 2023 and the official nomination will take place in February 2023.

1.2. Work package 2. A common science and policy Agenda

1.2.1. Task 2.1. Priority setting

Leader: ANSES (FR), ECHA (EU), EFSA (EU)

Participants: EAA (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), ISS (IT), GCSL (EL), DGS (PT)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing and implementing a well-structured and transparent prioritisation strategy through a fluid dialogue between WP2 and other Work Packages (WPs) and making a proposal for a systematic, criteria-based prioritisation for projects and substances.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

- PARC prioritisation process including a process for project review and approval

To ensure the delivery of PARC operational outcomes by the different work packages, most of the activities in PARC will be done through **projects** grouped and organised under the tasks/activities within the PARC work packages. In order to select projects that will be included in the rolling **SRIA (Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda)**, T2.1 partners prepared a **project review process** that contains the following phases:

- **Initiation Phase:** the project initiation request provides details on the project definition in terms of scope, data, risks and ethics and defines the partners involved in the project and the main budget requirements. The document is submitted to task 2.1 and is reviewed according to the developed criteria. The objective of the criteria is that the projects are fit for purpose so that the knowledge generated within PARC can contribute to EU and/or national regulatory science and policymaking. Further to the analysis of the relevance of the project, the projects that have been recommended through the Decision Memo submitted to the MB will enter the planning phase and will be added to the PARC rolling SRIA.
- **Planning phase:** the project planning document specifies the project scope, the schedule for the planned tasks (which could be divided in several steps) and an estimate of the necessary resources. The document is established by the project team and once agreed and finalised, it is considered as a reference document for the project, agreed on by the partners and integrated in the PARC budget.
- **Implementation phase:** this phase starts when the project team implements the project and produces the intermediate reports as outlined in the project plan. The monitoring process is organised by the Project Manager and the Task Leaders in close collaboration with the CT. The project implementation document will be updated each year and will be used for the production of the PARC ASR/AWP.
- **Closing phase:** the Project Manager ensures that the final report produced is accepted by the WPLs/TLs. All project documents are correctly filled and archived and all resources used by the project are formally released. A project financial report is produced and the budget line is closed. The project ends at this date.

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An Excel file (PARC Projects cluster) with the list of the Tasks, Activities and related Projects for each WP is regularly updated on the PARC ANSES SharePoint. The Excel file also includes the names of the contact points and reviewers assigned to projects for project review during the different phases.

The project review process has been made available to the consortium on 12 September on the PARC ANSES SharePoint after approval by MB. The project review process and criteria has been approved by the GB on 21st November (MS4). Projects description's fiches have been updated according to these criteria.

For Year 2, 7 new projects have been reviewed by T2.1 Contact Points and reviewers. Finally, 5 new projects have been included in PARC Project Portfolio in Annex of the AWPY2 (it has to be noted that one of these 5 new projects has been included as a new case study, part of the WP6 project P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU of Year 1) and 60 projects are in the implementation phase.

➤ Prioritisation criteria for substances and methods

D2.1. Prioritisation criteria report (due date M9, January 2023) is being prepared in order to map the prioritisation criteria that have been already applied by PARC WP/Task leaders to select the compounds and methods included in the first AWP. To feed this Deliverable, a survey on prioritisation criteria for substances has been prepared. Questions are related to the following main criteria: regulatory status, hazardous properties, exposure characteristics and technical feasibility. The survey has been sent to WPLs/TLs end of October 2022 and analyses of responses have been used to draft the deliverable 2.1 by the end of November 2022. In parallel to the survey on prioritisation criteria for substances, discussions have been organised with WPLs 4-5-6 to identify the prioritisation process for methods.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS4	Approval of prioritisation criteria for projects	ANSES	30/11/2022 (M7)	21/11/2022 (M7)	Approval by GB on 21 November 2022
D2.1	Prioritisation criteria report	ANSES	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.2.2. Task 2.2. Knowledge management and uptake into policy

Leader: BfR (DE), INSA (PT)

Participants: AUTH (EL), UOB (UK)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Making conceptual developments and implementation of network and communication structure of the ad hoc network of international and external partners for

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NGRAroute, scoping study to conceptually develop the information/knowledge management framework for PARCopedia as well as its implementation, and nomination of the Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs).

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

After the start of the project in May 2022, Task 2.2 was launched and partner commitment and interest to participate in specific activities were investigated. An online kick-off meeting with Task 2.2 partners was organised on June 3, 2022. In this meeting the activities to be developed under Task 2.2 were presented to the partners, as well as the organisation structure proposed by the Task co-leaders. Key features of PARCopedia and PARCroute were identified; a table of contents for the scoping study (PARCopedia) and a pre-structure of the first strategic roadmap (PARCroute, NGRA route) were brainstormed at a physical meeting held in Thessaloniki, Greece, on 13 and 14 October 2022. During these meetings, the future work under Task 2.2 was structured into work items, and commitments to lead and/or participate in the “task forces” created to address these items under the overall coordination of the Task 2.2 co-leaders were collected from the participants.

Regarding two of the deliverables of Task 2.2, i.e. a) an interim report on the progress with the NGRA roadmap (D2.3) and b) the scoping study for PARCopedia (D2.2). The collection of all the outputs from the individual task forces is planned to be complete by the end of the first annual work plan in April 2023. Until then, progress of the individual task forces will be monitored by means of regular online meetings.

Procedures and Terms of Reference (ToR) for the nomination and role of Chemical Leaders (CLs) and Methodology Leaders (MLs) were developed, including a description of their tasks and responsibilities. Online meetings with the CT and partners were organised to obtain information concerning HBM4EU’s experience with the Chemical Group Leaders. The procedures and ToR were presented to and discussed with the MB at several MB meetings. An overview of the chemicals and methodologies being addressed under PARC was performed in order to identify the chemicals and methodologies proposed to have leaders. The procedures for the nomination and the ToR for the CLs and MLs were discussed by the MB. The official nomination of the CLs and MLs will take place in Spring 2023.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D2.2	PARCopedia scoping study	BfR	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
D2.3	PARCroute roadmap 1	BfR	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
MS9	Definition of the orientations of PARCroute	BfR	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

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1.2.3. Task 2.3. Sustainability

Leader: INSERM (FR), NPHC (HU)

Participants: DOMG (BE)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing a process for continuous dialogue with the National Hub Contact Points (NHCPs) on needs and a concept for capacity building, start developing an exit strategy and further developing and refining the monitoring framework with T1.3.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

The survey focusing on the mapping of the existing knowledge gaps, requests, suggestions and expertise of the NHs was elaborated and launched during the second semester of 2022. This survey was applied to involve the NHs in the identification of PARC activities that need to be sustainable. Together with WP9, the basis of the peer-to-peer learning process were elaborated. Along the same lines a survey on the exit strategy was prepared and launched after that of the NH. The partners involved in this task first identified the major activities in PARC that need to be sustainable and included these in the survey. The survey is sent to the NH and asks them to prioritize the activities carried out in PARC that need to be sustained. HBM and the corresponding laboratory network have already been prioritized in HBM4EU, and it will obviously remain a priority for PARC. The other activities cover most of those of PARC, but they need to be prioritized by the NH and this task will then focus on those prioritized activities. The following activities are listed in the survey: environmental monitoring (taking into consideration current monitoring activities that are routinely carried out), non targeted screening activities both on human samples and environmental samples (taking into account the progress made in HBM4EU, other EU networks and the EIRENE ESFRI), New Approach Methodologies (NAMs) that are both developed in PARC but also in other EU clusters such as EURION and ASPIS; computational toxicology such as PBTk and AOP development, safe by design tools that are currently developed in PARC and in other EU projects, risk assessment activities and the national hub networks. Based on the survey outcomes, priorities will be identified and possibly other activities will be added and considered.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

Not Applicable.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.3. Work package 3. Synergies, collaborations and awareness

1.3.1. Task 3.1. Building effective interactions

Leader: EAA (AT), AUTH (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AGES (AT), EEA (EU), UBA (DE), IUSS (IT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), NIB (SI), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), GCSL (EL)

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Specific objective of the task for Y1: Setting up and running the International Board (IB) and Stakeholder Forum (SF), ensuring the representativeness of stakeholders from different sectors in the SF and that a high level IB is formed and, if relevant, assigning the PARC Ambassador.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A3.1.1. Establishment and running the Stakeholder Forum

The first Stakeholder Forum (SF) meeting is scheduled online in early 2023. The task co-leaders from EEA are responsible for the preparation and set up of the annual SFs. A kick-off meeting with Activity 3.1.1 partners took place to start the work on the establishment of the SF. Several meetings were held in order to develop and discuss the criteria to select stakeholders (Partners, MB, NHC) and to prepare the open call for membership in the PARC SF. The process was presented at a MB meeting and the feedback received was integrated in the document including the selection criteria. Finally, an open Call was distributed in October.

A timeline for the activities proposed to conclude the selection of SF members and for information and approval of the proposed SF members by the MB and the GSB (December 2022) was developed. Co-design of Online SF event together with partners (agenda (tour-de-table, get-to-know, memorandum of understanding for SF participation, etc.), communication and management of registration of SF members) was performed (November and December 2022).

➤ A3.1.2 Establishment and running of the International Board (IB)

The criteria for selection of the IB members were prepared in cooperation with the partners involved and was presented at a MB Meeting for endorsement. In addition, the rules of procedure of the IB were also completed.

Concerning the IB, a list of potential participants was prepared, according to their recognised expertise and high-level functions and an invitation was sent, including a previously prepared CV template. An algorithm was used to evaluate the candidates based on the CV provided and a list of potential members of the IB, together with the rules of procedure, was presented to the MB, and the GSB for approval.

The first IB Meeting started to be prepared and is planned to be held in the first trimester of 2023. Strategies to manage the expectations from PARC and the IB members and maximise their inputs were discussed with the partners in order to be presented and discussed at the first meeting.

Deliverable 3.3 was prepared for submission at M9.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS5	Establishment of SF, IB	EEA/AUTH	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
D3.3	Report on the establishment of the interactions with SF IB and ambassadors	EEA/AUTH	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.3.2. Task 3.2. Communication, dissemination, and awareness

Leader: EEA (EU), NPHC (HU)

Participants: ANSES (FR), SpF (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), UMIT (AT), VITO (BE), DOMG (BE), CIPH (CR), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), HB (EE), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), BfR (DE), UI (IS), MOH-IL (IL), ISS (IT), UNINA (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), RIVM (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIOM (PL), FMUL (PT), INSA (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), SZU (SK), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), ISCIH (ES), KEMI (SE), SLV (SE), FOPH (CH), UKHSA (UK), UOB (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing and implementing the communication strategy for PARC

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

The graphical identity for PARC was produced based on ideas previously collected and discussed with the MB and the CT. It includes, among others, the logo package, graphic rollouts, templates and visual guidelines. A company contracted by EEA upon negotiated procedure, gave support with the branding, interactive media design and communication support services for PARC.

Development of the PARC website: The navigation menu was drafted and discussed with the CT and all WP co-leaders. A service request was claimed at EEA and the web development was started in December 2022.

Deliverable 3.2 on the PARC communication and dissemination strategy was prepared with the partners involved and submitted in due time (beginning of M7).

A working group on risk communication was set up and a literature search was performed to establish a common strategy on risk communication. A roadmap for the activities was prepared and discussed.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D3.1	PARC website	EEA	31/07/2022 (M3)	Ongoing	This deliverable was delayed due to constraints with the procurement procedure to subcontract external services to design and develop the website. It has been internally shared with PARC participants by the end of December 2022 (M8). A first version of the PARC website will be launched in January 2023 (M9).

D3.2	Communication and dissemination strategy	NPHC	31/10/2022 (M6)	09/11/2022 (M7)	No significant delay
MS8	Development of the overall architecture for information sharing	VITO	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

The procurement procedure took more time than it was foreseen. EEA could not initiate the necessary procurement procedures for subcontracting of external services until the receipt of the amount of prefinancing (as of 23 August 2022) due to the constraints of the EEA financial regulation.

1.3.3. Task 3.3. Networking and Synergies

Leader: INSA (PT), NKUA (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), MU (CZ), UBA (DE), FMUL (PT), APA (PT), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIJZ (SI), EFET (EL), UOC (EL), BPI (EL), GCSL (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Exploring and establishing collaborations and synergies with other relevant scientific/regulatory/policy initiatives at national, EU and international level.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

The rules for the establishment of an official synergy between external projects and PARC were created. The procedure was discussed among the partners of T3.3. In total, three web forms were created

- 1) The first form will be used for the expression of interest by external projects/activities to collaborate with PARC;
- 2) The second form will establish synergy with clear goals and timeline after the approval of the WP and task co-leaders;
- 3) The third form will contribute to the evaluation of the efficiency of the synergy and of the satisfaction of the external partners.

The forms will be made available on PARC’s website. The aim is to map the synergies in a database and stimulate the cooperation with external projects by proposing further collaborations when possible. Moreover, the forms aim to create quantitative measures of the performance of PARC regarding synergies. The monitoring procedure is expected to demonstrate the effectiveness of PARC in acting as a central project for bringing together other EU projects and activities.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
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D3.4	Database and roadmap for SYNnet	INSA/NKUA	28/02/2023 (M10)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
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Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.4. Work package 4. Monitoring and Exposure

1.4.1. Task 4.1. Human Biomonitoring

Leader: VITO (BE), ISCIII (ES)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CEA (FR), CSIC (ES), EAA (AT), EHESP (FR), FFA (FI), TTL (FI), FISABIO (ES), FOPH (CH), HSE (UK), KI (SE), IMROH (HR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), INSERM (FR), INSST (ES), IOM (UK), IPA (DE), KUM (DE), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), KU Leuven (BE), LNS (LU), LSMU (LT), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MOH (IL), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), MUW (AT), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), NPHSL (LT), ONIRIS (FR), UKHSA (UK), PIH (BE), REGIONH-RH (DK), RSU (LV), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), STAMI (NO), SZU-CZ (CZ), SZU-SK (SK), THL (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UGent (BE), UGR (ES), UH (BE), ULFFA (SI), ULPGC (ES), ULUND (SE), UMU (SE), UMIL (IT), UNINA (IT), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), UNIVIE (AT), UNN (NO), UOULU (FI), UOC (EL), UPV/EHU (ES), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WULS-SGGW (PL), CIPH (HR), SHSO (CY), SDU (DK), Fraunhofer-IBMT (DE), UFZ (DE), NPHC (HU), UI (IS), VSCHT (CZ), EASP (ES), SECO (CH),

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Finalising study design and developing supporting materials for the general population survey, targeted surveys and occupational surveys, identifying exposure and effect biomarkers, proposing innovative (sampling) techniques for Human Bio-Monitoring (HBM) surveys and elaborating a roadmap to explore the links between prioritised exposures and health outcomes

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A4.1.1 Design, alignment and fieldwork of HBM studies

The ultimate goal of this activity is to perform a range of overarching activities to promote the optimal use of supporting common materials conducive to comparable EU HBM data. The initial focus is placed on the update and further elaboration when needed of the materials developed in HBM4EU. We have established 3 working groups (WG), each focusing on one aspect of the work: i) review and update of materials (Fraunhofer, LNS, CIPH, EAA, EASP, IMROH, INSA, ISCIII, ISSeP, ISS, JSI, PIH, RSU, SpF, STAMI, UBA, ULUND, UPV/EHU, UOULU); ii) identify and address areas of needs and improvements in PARC (SpF, IDAEA-CSIC, CIPH, FOPH, Fraunhofer, EASP, IMROH, INSA, ISCIII, ISSeP, JSI, LNS, LSMU, NIJZ, NIOM, PIH, RSU, STAMI, THL, UBA, UMU, UOULU); iii) explore and propose solutions for inclusion of novel aspects in HBM studies implementation (ISCIII, SpF, CIPH, EASP, INSA, JSI, LNS, MUW, NIJZ, PIH, UBA, UMU, MOH-IL). Priority have been set in the first WG around the update of the informed consent in line with GDPR and the format-lay out of the forms for the general and occupational surveys. The second WG will define a minimal set of obligatory

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questions and refine the questions considering the research and policy question and the mandatory variables in collaboration with 4.1.4 – data management. Solutions for the digitalisation of collection of information will be explored by the third WG who will provide guidance documents to inform the choices in the use of secure web applications for managing online surveys and databases.

Projects progress (as described in the AWP1 SRIA):

S4.1.1.1. Development of supporting materials for harmonized EU HBM conduct

No project submitted at present

S4.1.1.2 General population survey

- **P4.1.1.2.a_Y1_GenHBMSurvey_VITO:** The general survey design has been developed by a core group of partners. Task 4.1 partners are contacted to collect information on planned HBM studies to check if they fulfil the study design criteria to contribute to the PARC general survey. First selection of studies is performed (to be finalised early 2023).

S4.1.1.3. Targeted Surveys

No project submitted at present

S4.1.1.4 Occupational surveys

- **P4.1.1.4.a_Y1_OccupFeasability_TTL:** Cd, PAHs and BPA were selected as priority substances for this study. General population surveys which have collected data on these substances have been identified. The study owners were approached during October to evaluate the available information on participants occupations and their willingness to share the data with the research group. Altogether 12 potential studies were identified for further evaluation. Final selection of studies will be made by beginning of March. This is followed by the identification of relevant occupational groups, coding of occupations and data analyses.
- **P4.1.1.4.b_Y1_SentinelSystem_KULeuven:** A mapping exercise was performed among the participating countries (KUL, INSA, MU, UGR, AU, LNS, RUMC, DPH-UNINA, SpF, BPI; no answers from NIOM, ULUND, RSU and UNISANTE yet) to map in detail which institutes could contribute via sample collection, and which would only be able to contribute via questionnaires. Later on it was decided that the Sentinel Surveillance Project would not be embedded within the general survey, so that no samples could be collected, and all institutes would only collect questionnaire data. .
- **P4.1.1.4.c_Y1_HealthCareSurvey_TTL_RUMC:** The outline of the occupational healthcare project was defined together with TTL, MU, ENSP, INRS, LNS, RUMC, ISS, UNINA, UMIL, UNIPD, RSU, SGGW, IOM, identifying the aims and scope of the project. The project will focus on hazardous medicinal products, inhalation anaesthetics and disinfection/cleaning products (biocides). So far, specific substances suitable for biomonitoring have been identified from each of these three groups. These include 12 cytotoxics, 5 anesthetic substances and 2 disinfectants. Further selection is made before M12 on the basis of the information received from hospitals regarding the most commonly used substances. These exposures will primarily be studied in hospital settings in 10+ EU member states. Potential biomarkers of exposure were identified. Relevant effect biomarkers applied in the study will be decided in collaboration with P4.1.3.3a (Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns). Supporting occupational hygiene measurements were identified with RUMC, TTL, ISS, UNINA, MU and INRS. Partners have expressed their initial interest to be involved

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in analyses to be discussed with the quality assurance working group (QAWG Activity 4.1.2 .2). Interested hospitals have been already contacted in several countries. The aim is to recruit at least two hospitals per country. Recruitment can only start after ethics approval of the final study protocol (estimated M11-M15 depending on procedures for evaluation of study protocols that may be different from one country to the other).

- **P4.1.1.4d_Y1_OccupWaste_ENSP_TTL:** The outline of the occupational waste management project was defined with the partners involved. The main waste streams that will be the focus of the project have been defined and include electrical waste and plastic waste from different sources. Potential exposures in these activities and related exposure biomarkers have been identified. Relevant effect biomarkers are currently defined in collaboration with project P4.1.3.3a (Roadmap to explore the links between prioritized chemical substances exposure and health concerns). Afterwards, all the partners identified which type of waste management companies they could reach in their countries and analytical capacities available in their labs to measure some of the substances and respective biomarkers already identified as relevant for each waste stream. This will be discussed further with 4.1.2. Next steps will be for ENSP and TTL to prepare a first draft study design that can be used to approach waste management companies and ethical committees in each country and to start with all the partners revising the existing SOP available from HBM4EU e-waste study and develop new SOP when needed.

S4.1.1.5. Implementation of innovative methods

No project submitted at present

- A4.1.2 Supporting activities progress: Laboratory analysis and quality assurance

No projects were planned for AWP Y1.

S4.1.2.1. Define the best suited exposure biomarkers (matrix/chemical) and analytical methods for the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC

S4.1.2.2. Ensure the quality and comparability of the analytical HBM data through a flexible Quality Assurance/Quality Control (QA/QC) programme to cover the needs of the specific HBM studies addressed in PARC

S4.1.2.3. Explore new QA/QC approaches to support the use of innovative techniques in HBM surveys in PARC

S4.1.2.4. Harmonise analytical methods across laboratories and define reference analytical methods when possible

S4.1.2.5. Analyse the exposure biomarkers in the samples emerging from human biomonitoring task

S4.1.2.6. Analyse effect biomarkers in samples emerging from the human biomonitoring task

Under 4.1.2 the working groups for the different aspects related to QA/QC and chemical analyses have been created identifying sub-activities coordinators (S4.1.2.1 LNS; S4.1.2.2 ISCIII; S4.1.2.3 ONIRIS; S4.1.2.4 NIPH; S4.1.2.5 SCIENSANO; S4.1.2.6 UGR), key contributors and other partners. Meetings and discussions have also been held with T4.2, T4.3 and T9.3 for coordination. Work has been initiated towards the definition of criteria to select the best biomarkers and analytical methods for chemical analysis in HBM surveys in PARC. The Quality Assurance Working Group (QAWG) has been created, the members are ISCIII, AU, IPA, JSI, NIPH, UAntwerpen, and WUR. A working document to define the needs for QA and comparability of the HBM data generated under T4.1 has been prepared to initiate the work together with T9.1 and T9.3.

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➤ A4.1.3 Link exposure and health related information

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

S4.1.3.1 Propose health-based HBM guidance values

- **P4.1.3.1.a_Y1_Derivation of HBM-GVs_UBA:** Within the framework of PARC project 4.1.3.1a, four substance dossiers as basis for the derivation of HBM-GVs have been drafted in year 1, respectively for DHHB (Uvinul A plus), lamda cyhalothrin, aluminium and nickel. Proposals for HBM-GVs are first discussed within the project and then forwarded to the national hubs for further comment and approval.

UBA has taken the lead for DHHB (Diethylamino hydroxybenzoyl hexyl benzoate, CAS no. 302776-68-7, trade name: Uvinul® A Plus), and lamda cyhalothrin. For the last-mentioned substance there is already a provisional HBM-GV, which did not undergo a consultation process within HBM4EU. Therefore, a detailed substance dossier will now be submitted and it will be checked if the value can be adopted. The derivation of the provisional HBM-GV for benzophenone-3 under HBM4EU will be summarized and also be submitted for consultation under PARC. The HBM-GVs for DHHB and the corresponding substance dossier are currently reviewed by project partners. ANSES has taken the lead for aluminium and is currently working on a national OEL and a corresponding HBM-GV as well as HBM-GVs for the general population. TTL has taken the lead for nickel. NIPH-FHI and TTL agreed to work on mercury in 2023. It is to be examined whether and, if so, which significant published toxicological findings need to be added to the dossier in the HBM4EU Deliverable D 5.12. The findings on the toxicology of mercury presented in the HBM4EU Deliverable D 13.7 should also be taken into account. Based on this, it should be clarified whether the provisional HBM-GVs for the general population (7 µg Hg/l urine, 3.5 µg Hg/l blood) which were derived within HBM4EU can be adopted. AUTH offered support regarding modelling work. A task group on chromates has been established by Radboudumc with collaboration of TTL, Unisante, SECO and partly ANSES which will work on Chromium VI. The need is seen to complement the existing HBM4EU dossier and risk-related value on chromium VI with regard to correlations of lower air concentrations and body burden. A further task group was suggested by MOH-IL and NIPH-FHI with the focus on PFAS, whose work could particularly benefit from being planned for a longer period of time to incorporate results from other work packages. Additionally, partners agreed to check which other international institutions derive similar health-related guidance values as the HBM-GV and to what extent these values can be adopted to avoid duplication of work. First contacts to T6.2.3 on real life mixtures have been established. Virtual meetings with the partners take place every 4 to 8 weeks, a face-to-face meeting in Berlin is planned for 2023.

S4.1.3.2. Identify effect biomarkers for prioritized chemicals, populations and health outcomes

No project submitted at present

S4.1.3.3 Link human biomonitoring studies to health examination and dietary surveys

- **P4.1.3.3.a_Y1_RoadmapLinkingHBMhealth_SpF_VITO:** This project aims to develop a roadmap that identifies concrete actions to promote research on the link between chemical exposures and health outcomes through biomarkers of effect. A mapping exercise and literature

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review was initiated to get an overview of up-to-date information on biomarkers of effects for prioritized substances in relation to PARC priority health endpoints. Meetings and discussions have been held with partners for coordination and distribution of work. Building further on health parameters information collected in HBM4EU, partners (EAA, EHESP, Fraunhofer, IDAEA-CSIC, INSST, JSI, KU Leuven, LNS, NIJZ, UKHSA, RSU, SpF, TTL, UBA) have also compiled an inventory of different metrics of health outcomes and health measurements for each substance/group of substances of interest in the general and first occupational surveys. In light of the information gathered, a list of validated health measurements is made and criteria are being applied to determine the number and the type of measurements that should be considered in the surveys in relation to PARC research interest in age groups and policy questions. Recommendations will be made on key health-related information to be included in the surveys questionnaires that can help better capture health status in relation to family history, lifestyle, diet and living environment. The feasibility of the implementation of effect biomarkers has been initiated with the identification of effect biomarkers for the prioritised chemicals for the suggested health endpoints (AU, AUTH, EAA, TTL, INRS, INSA, INSERM, ISCIII, JSI, LNS, MU, NIJZ, NLZOH, SECO, SpF, UGR, ULPGC, UU-IRAS, VITO).

➤ A4.1.4 Data management and analysis

Evaluation and adaptation of HBM4EU basic data format. Evaluation and adaptation of scripts to perform QC of the data, to calculate additional data and to calculate aggregated data from the individual data templates. Development of web application to perform these scripts locally. Further maintenance of the European HBM dashboard and PEH data platform.

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

S4.1.4.1. Data management

No project submitted at present

S4.1.4.2 Data analysis

- **P4.1.4.2.a_Y1_DataAnalysisHBM4EU_VITO:** An inventory of available HBM4EU data and research questions explored during HBM4EU is made. Core team selected unexplored research questions (RQs) of interest for PARC. A document is elaborated with an overview of the selected RQs and reasoning behind it. Partners are identified that will take up the statistical analyses. Steps are initiated to submit requests for data access to the individual data to the PEH data platform for each of the lead partners to get approval for data use of the HBM4EU Aligned Studies or MoM-study. For the occupational and SPECIMEn studies, agreements will be renewed in the respective networks.

➤ A4.1.5 Preparation of a sustainable monitoring and surveillance system for Europe

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P4.1.5.a_Y1_SustainHBMSystem_VITO:** project activities will start from M9.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

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No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD4.1	Periodic report on available supporting materials for HBM studies	VITO/ISCIII	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD4.2	Periodic report on analytical methods and measurements for exposure and effect biomarkers	VITO/ISCIII	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD4.3	Derivation of HBM-GVs (one dossier per substance; 3-4 substances)	VITO/ISCIII	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
MS10	Finalisation of study design for the HBM	VITO/ISCIII	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problems encountered.

1.4.2. Task 4.2. Environmental and multisource monitoring

Leader: INERIS (FR), AU (DK)

Participants: ANSES (FR), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CNRS (FR), CNR-IRSA (IT), CSIC (ES), CSTB (FR), EA (UK), EAWAG (CH), EFET (EL), Fraunhofer-IME (DE), FISABIO (ES), INRAE (FR), INSERM (FR), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), IVL (SE), JSI (SI), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), NKUA (EL), OFB (FR), ONIRIS (FR), OVAM (BE), SCIENSANO (BE), SLU (SE), SYKE (FI), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UCLM (PT), UFZ (DE), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UniLU (LU), VITO (BE), VSCHT (CZ), ISCIII (ES), VUA (NL), NILU (NO), UKCEH (UK), BPI (EL), NMBU (NO), SpF (FR)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Establishing a prioritisation process that supports EU and environmental legislations and performing environmental and multisource monitoring in relation to issues of regulatory and policy concern in a case study

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

T4.2 has worked on the project P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey and prepared a new project P4.2.1_2_Monitoringframe. Activities in the first project have mainly been related to 4.2.2, i.e. the review of existing knowledge. Here, a detailed characterisation of the compound groups of this project (PFAS and endocrine disruption compounds) has taken place, including chemical identities and physico-chemical properties, and a review of the state-of-the-art of analytical methods has been initiated. The preparation for the second project have focussed on information collection towards an inventory of existing prioritisation processes.

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA)

T4.2 has initiated a first inventory of existing prioritisation schemes, as a preparatory work for the development of a framework for automated assessment and prioritisation of chemicals/matrices/endpoints deserving attention for future monitoring projects. This activity will be continued in 2023, including a series of workshops / meetings.

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The complex task of environmental monitoring is being established in a pilot project:

(P4.2.a_Y1_ENVMonitoringPilotSurvey_INERIS_AU) on the monitoring of per-/polyfluorinated alkylated substances (PFAS) and endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) (“*Establishment of the overall process of environmental and multisource monitoring with the help of a pilot study addressing PFAS and endocrine disruptors*”). This pilot project consists of multiple steps, with the first one focussing on the review of existing knowledge, to avoid any duplication of work. This central activity has been further defined and described in a more specific work plan, including a characterisation of the chemical groups, a review of analytical methods for EDCs and PFAS, procedures for sample exchange and a survey to collect information on existing samples and data. Four project leaders were appointed to lead sub-activities on the characterisation of the compound groups and the review of analytical methods, for EDC and PFAS, respectively. Five sequential meetings were organised by the task leaders in the period of June to September 2022 to involve all partners in this work.

In this phase, a comprehensive compilation of EDC lists already identified and assessed by regulatory bodies at EU and national level has been compiled, including EFSA assessment, Edlist.org and the ANSES list based on the Deduct screening work. Additionally, some other relevant lists of potential EDCs were added (hormones, bisphenols, etc.), including inputs from ECHA. Finally, all substances in the NORMAN SusDat database were screened using the EDC prediction models of the (QSAR) VEGA platform and the EDC active compounds were added to the master list. The compiled list was curated and information about all relevant metadata (matrices, physico-chemical properties, functional groups for chemical analysis, modes of action for the application of bioassays, relevant matrices, use sectors, etc.) were collected thanks to the contribution of the partners.

A similar approach was applied for PFAS. Two questionnaires were circulated to collect information about PFAS that are covered by current regulation (e.g. Water Framework Directive, Groundwater Directive, etc.) and EU initiatives (e.g. HBM4EU) as well as PFAS compounds that are currently analysed in the partners’ labs. In addition to that, information about the chemical class, availability of standards, relevant matrices, sectors of use, etc. were compiled in a master table. This characterisation of the compound groups, i.e. the collection of information on the compound groups, their physico-chemical properties, use areas etc., is expected to be finalised before the end of 2022.

The activity on the review of state-of-the-art of analytical methods is intended to result in review papers for PFAS and EDCs, respectively. The manuscript for PFAS is currently being drafted, focusing on their performance / critical aspects for environmental monitoring purposes.

To complete the process of review of existing knowledge, a systematic and comprehensive compilation of information / data about existing projects, monitoring campaigns (recent, on-going, planned) on PFAS and EDC is needed and fine-tuning the work among the WPs is crucial before the launch of a survey among all partners. A template for compilation of such information has been drafted and proposed for discussion with WP7 and WP9.

In order to establish procedures for exchange of samples (re-use of existing samples, for example from Environmental Specimen Banks or collected in research projects), a meeting was organised with the key partners and the coordinator of the LIFE APEX project, in view of wider discussion in a workshop due to be organised early 2023 (protocols for sample handling, metadata, QA/QC aspects, data ownership, etc.).

The work in T4.2 has been coordinated with other WPs, in a series of meetings, involving T4.1, T4.3, T6.2, WP7, and WP9. The T4.2 co-leads are represented in the QA/QC Core Group established in T9.3, and first proposals for the QA/QC concept supporting the upcoming monitoring exercise were discussed

in this group. General procedures, including criteria for laboratory selection, were proposed for contacts to laboratories in synergy with WP9. Moreover, work on establishing a data flow plan in collaboration with WP7 in line with the whole PARC DMP started. A data champion for T4.2 has been appointed.

This project contributes to AD4.4 and AD4.5, as specified in the table below. Due to delays in the scientific work (as specified in the section “Problems encountered”) we expect some delay with these additional deliverables.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD4.4	Procedures for agreement on transparent use of existing data, access to samples and involvement of external laboratories	INERIS/AU	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	We expect a delay of three months (M15), see section on “Problems encountered”.
AD4.5	Technical specifications of the study (project design, hypothesis and research question as well as analytical procedures including QA/QC and data flows)	INERIS/AU	30/04/2023(M12)	Ongoing	We expect a delay of three months (M15), see section on “Problems encountered”.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

The beginning of PARC in May 2022 had implications for the initial activities as summer holidays affected the continuity of the work. The T4.2 co-leaders maintained meeting activities and continued the work over the holiday period, but not all partners could participate, and response periods were longer than usual. Some activities in the start-up phase took longer than expected or had not been factored in when developing the first AWP: Establishing effective communication tools, e.g. the sharepoint site, mailing lists, templates for meeting minutes etc., was time-consuming and had to be covered with the resources primarily foreseen for scientific work. We have also experienced a variety of expectations in the partner group, which have taken and will probably continue to take time in the discussions. The development and implementation of projects required more administrative work than originally anticipated.

1.4.3. Task 4.3. Innovative methods and tools for monitoring and surveys

Leader: INRAE (FR), VUA (NL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AU (DK), BfG (DE), BRGM (FR), CEA (FR), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), EHESP (FR), INERIS (FR), INRS (FR), , IRFM (IT), JSI (SI), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), ONIRIS (FR), ORU (SE), SLU (SE), SpF (FR), UAntwerpen (BE), UBA (DE), UBAH (UK), UCPH (DK), UFZ (DE), UGR (ES), UniLU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UU-IRAS (NL), VITO (BE), WR (NL), AUTH (EL), BPI (GR), CNR-IRSA (IT), EV-ILVO (NL), FMUL (PT), GeoZS (SI), CSIC (ES), , IISPV (ES),

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ISCIH (ES), ISS (IT), IVL (SE), JU (CZ), KUM (DE), LNE (FR), NIB (SI), NIJZ (SI), NILU (NO), NIOM (PL), OFB (FR), STAMI (NO), SU (SE), SYKE (FI), THL (FI), TNO (NL), UG-AT (AT), UG-PL (PL), UKCEH (UK), UL (LV), ULFFA (SI), UNIADBN (UK), VSCHT (CZ), WULS-SGGW (PL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Fostering the permeability and harmonisation between the environment-food-HBM communities and prioritised strategic development of innovative approaches from sampling to suspect/non-targeted/Effect-Directed Analysis (EDA) driven exposure data generation and related data processing

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

Six projects have been elaborated in year 1, in line with the roadmap established for task 4.3., which were primarily designed by the co-lead teams. These projects were then all started as planned, under the lead of the respectively appointed project leader teams.

➤ A4.3.1 Transversal actions

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P4.3.1.a_Y1_T01-Concept Paper_MU:** this project relates on alignment of main concepts and strategical vision regarding innovative methods.
- **P4.3.1.b_Y1_T02-QAQC Issues_WR:** this project relates to definition and harmonisation of QA/QC Issues for SS/NTS/EAD approaches
- **P4.3.1.c_Y1_T03-EWStools_SLU:** this project relates to relevant contribution to Early Warning System
- **P4.3.1.d_Y1_T04-Data Processing Workflow_EHESP:** this projects relates to the elaboration of integrated Data Processing Workflow

➤ A4.3.2 Human samples based proof-of-concepts

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA)

- **P4.3.2.a_Y1_H01-Perinatal exposure_INRAE:** this project relates to two first proof-of-concept applications focused on perinatal exposure

➤ A4.3.3 Environment samples based proof-of-concepts

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA)

- **P4.3.3.a_Y1_E01-Wastewater based epidemiology_UFZ-UBATH:** this project relates to wastewater based epidemiology

➤ A4.3.4 Food samples based proof-of-concepts

No project submitted at present

Formation of those project groups was addressed based on expressions of interest and expertise, and permitted to embed the majority of partners interested to contribute to the task. Most of the corresponding project kick-off meetings were organised and the further refinement and co-built detailed description and structuration of these projects are in progress

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List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD4.6	Concept paper regarding common definitions and short to medium term support to policy objectives of innovative (self-) sampling, suspect screening and NTS/EDA approaches	INRAE/VUA	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

Difficulty to cope with requests from new partners willing to contribute in the task, and who were not initially included as contributors to the task, and to manage both capacity building and respect of common rules established for partner consultation and integration. Difficulty to have a consolidated vision on partner's allocated resources due to discrepancies between budget data expressed by individual partners to the task co-lead teams and budget data as aggregated at their institutional level and possibly top-down adjusted at WP and/or whole project coordination level.

1.5. Work package 5. Hazard Assessment

1.5.1. Task 5.1. Toxicity testing addressing data gaps of concern

Leader: NIPH (NO), INSA (PT), BPI (EL)

Participants:

Activity 5.1.1: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), AfR (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), IBMT (DE), IMR (NO), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIPH (NO), NVI (NO), Sciensano (BE), STAMI (NO), TTL (FL), ULFFA (SI), UMIL (IT), UNAV (ES), UNIVIE (AT), WU-TOX (NL)

Activity 5.1.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UPO (ES), UU (SE)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: In order to close regulatory/policy data gaps on hazards, our steps in Y1 have been:

- i) to gather regulatory/policy needs from EU and national agencies on BPA alternatives and test item availability for prioritised groups of compounds. This was achieved through the organization of a workshop with key stakeholders (M1-4; AD5.1);
- ii) planning OECD test guideline studies to be conducted in years 2 and 3 (e.g. Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Studies (EOGRTS) (AD5.2)) and iii) conducting first *in vitro* studies on prioritised substances (M5-12).

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

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➤ A5.1.1 Closing data gaps of concern for human health

Natural toxins were selected at the beginning of PARC as a group of substances of priority with data gaps on hazard for human health that can be closed in PARC. Analogues from the Enniatins and Alternaria mycotoxins were selected to close data gaps on genotoxicity, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity and some other selected hazards. Sourcing of the test items is ongoing. It is considered important that as much as possible the same batch of test item are used in the different studies. The first batches of test items are expected to be available late 2022. Two review papers are in preparation summarising the available data and identify data gaps.

For the first round of studies, aiming at closing regulatory/ policy data gaps on hazards, substances were selected through consultation with partners involved in hazard and risk assessment in national and European Agencies (2022 06 17 BPA Alternative/Analogues dedicated workshop, AD5.1). Concerning the BPA alternatives that will be assessed to close data gaps on human health hazard, several priority substances were identified and are indicated in the Table 1, below. However, not all substances will be assessed for all endpoints and the inclusion of other alternatives/analogues outside the priority list is also be considered for specific endpoint, as was duly justified in light of knowledge gaps for specific endpoints.

Table 1. List of Prioritised BPA alternatives and analogues

Substances	Human exposure/ concern	Data gaps (TK studies?)	Alerts	Regulatory needs
BPZ CAS# 843-55-0 REACH: No Data, Not registered	X	X		Group 1 Screening batteries
BPE	X	X		In specific cases, other halogenated BPA alternatives will be studied, like TBBPA / Tetrabromobisphenol A CAS# 79-94-7 Tonnage: 6.200 t/yr (2004)
BPS-MAE / p-[[p-benzoyloxyphenyl]sulfonyl]phenol CAS#63134-33-8	X	X**		
Pergafast 201 CAS# 232938-43-1 Tonnage: 100-1000t/yr	X	X**		
BPP CAS# 2167-51-3 No Data, Not registered ! Consider that it might be more a natural contaminant than a chemical pollutant	X	X		Group 2 Focused tested on endpoints of concern (toxicokinetics)
BPAP CA# 1571-75-1 Tonnage: 1-10t/yr	X	X		
TCBPA / Tetrachlorobisphenol CAS# 2664-63-3 No data, Not registered	X	X**		

The substances selected are based on data from UBA, REACH, partners and also the need of closing data gaps confirmed by ECHA (in blue)

8 substances will be tested out of the 17 preselected from *35 candidates
**labelled molecules

Furthermore, there have been ongoing planning of OECD test guideline studies to be conducted in years 2 and 3 (e.g. Extended One-Generation Reproductive Toxicity Studies (EOGRTS)).

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P5.1.1a_Y1_Toxins_Bfr_UNIVE:** in this project, data gaps on subforms of the mycotoxins Enniatins and Alternaria for human health will be closed. A number of discussions were held to

agree on a program of studies for genotoxic, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity and selected other hazards. Sourcing of test items is ongoing. It is considered important that the same batch of test item is used in all the studies. Two review papers summarising the existing knowledge and data gaps are in preparation.

- **P5.1.1.b_Y1_BPA_Human tox:** in this project, a meeting with stakeholders was organised to select the most relevant BPA analogues/alternatives for further testing (AD5.1). The selected chemicals will be tested for non-genotoxic carcinogenesis, endocrine disruption, immunotoxicity, developmental neurotoxicity, toxicokinetics and metabolism. Meetings to agree on a final program of studies are ongoing. One or two review papers summarising the existing data and data gaps are in preparation
- A5.1.2 Toxicity assessment addressing data gaps of concern (Environment)

Based on the prioritisation procedure followed within PARC, two groups of substances were selected for testing during the first years of the PARC in order to fill in the identified data gaps of concerns as regards the environmental health, *i.e.*, naturally occurring toxins and BPA alternatives (AD5.1), therefore two projects were planned and during the first months of PARC implementation of these projects were developed in more detail and additional partners were included.

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P5.1.2.a_Y1_NaturalToxinsAqua_Ugent** project initial discussions on the selection of the natural toxins to be tested were carried out and UAVR joined as partner. Each partner will focus on specific organisms, but to ensure maximum data gap filling and impact, the selection of compounds will be streamlined between partners as much as possible. For the selection of the compounds, the environmental relevance of certain toxins as well as the exposure through food was considered. A first list of identified potential candidate compounds to be tested was created (*i.e.*, microcystin, nodularin, yessotoxin, brevetoxin, okadaic acid) and further discussions will be carried out in the following period in order to finalise the list of individual compounds to be tested during Y2.
- **P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU** project, a workshop was organised and the regulatory and policy needs were discussed by the EU agencies and key stakeholders (2022 06 17 BPA Alternative/Analogues dedicated workshop, AD5.1). As an outcome of this workshop a list of BPA alternatives was provided for which data gaps were identified as regards their possible adverse effects for human and environmental health. In parallel a literature search was carried out to collect monitoring data on environmental realistic concentrations of BPA alternatives as detected in different environmental compartments *i.e.*, surface water, soil, sediment. The collection of monitoring data is currently on going. Finally, a review is under preparation in order to collect the available data and describe the identified regulatory gaps and needs.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

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No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD5.1	New title: Additional Deliverable AD5.1 List of prioritized BPA alternatives for WP5 Hazard Assessment activities Workshop Report WP5 (Previous title: Report on the workshop organised with national and EU agencies and stakeholders on the of-concern bisphenol A alternatives)	BPI/NIPH/INSA	31/01/2023 (M9)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD5.2	Report of the description of the EOGRT study to be conducted	BPI/NIPH/INSA	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

We experienced the common challenges when making e.g., 27 partners align in one project with very tight timelines. Specifically filling in all templates on time, but we are happy to apply different strategies and deliver the documents on time.

We have a problem with identifying project leaders among the PARC partners for the BPA projects since this role is still not clearly defined and the most relevant people are very busy. Sourcing of test items might be challenging and some partners cannot hire personnel since contracts between the GS and the AEs are not finalised. However, the WP5 co-leaders found a solution to solve the issue.

1.5.2. Task 5.2. Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Leader: DTU FOOD (DK), VUB (BE); 5.2.2: MU (CZ)

Participants:

Activity 5.2.1: AIT (AT), ANSES (FR), BfR (DE), DTU (DK), IfaDo (DE), INRAE (FR), INSA (FR), INSERM (FR), IRAS (NL), IRFMN (IT), ISCIII (ES), IUF (DE), LIH (LU), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NMBU (NO), NPHC (HU), RIVM (NL), SDU (DK), TiHo (DE), UAntwerpen (BE), UFZ (DE), UIBK (AT), UKHSA (UK), UKL (DE), UKON (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), ULFFA (SI), UNAV (ES), UU (SE); VUA (NL), VUB (BE), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.2.2: BfG (DE), BPI (EL), CNRS (FR), EAWAG (CH), IEP-NRI (PL), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), MU (CZ), MUI (AT), NIB (SI), NIC (SI), NIVA (NO), SDU (DK), SLU (SE), UAntwerpen (BE), UAVR (PT), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UGent (BE), UPO (ES), UU (SE)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing innovative methodologies that will directly aid chemical hazard identification, Risk Assessment (RA) and regulation/policy. WP5 will focus on five different endpoints (immunotoxicity, non-genotoxic carcinogenicity, (developmental) neurotoxicity, endocrine disruption (thyroid) and metabolic disruption).

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Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A5.2.1 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

• **P5.2.1.a_Y1_NGTX_BfR**

Project work related to the development of tests that can identify tissue and substance specific effects related to distinct aspects of non-genotoxic carcinogenesis have been initiated. During the first 6 months, all the available assays and cellular models available at the different partners' laboratories were listed. The most suitable assays to be conducted notably to avoid redundancy between labs were defined (needed for AD5.3). Currently, the list of NGTXCs chemicals to be tested to analyse the accuracy of the different assays is worked on (INRAE, BfR, ANSES, INSERM, NIB, UL-LACDR, UNAV, IRFM, RIVM, UKHSA, UKL, NILU).

• **P5.2.1.b_Y1_MD-EDC_INRAE**

The development of a battery of metabolic disrupting chemicals (MDC)-specific NAMs based on human as well as non-human models has been initiated. This work includes a comprehensive exploration of Nuclear Receptor (NR)-driven effects using stably transfected cell lines, NAMs encompassing hepatic and non-hepatic *in vitro* systems including multi-tissue cross-talk, a deep mechanistic exploration of key cellular pathways using human *in vitro* models, as well as parallel additional 3R-compliant models and novel methods, including imagery (needed for AD5.3). Synergies with ongoing projects such as the EURION cluster have been identified, the spectrum of MDC has been extended and there was active participation in the selection process of PARC priority-listed families of substances (INRAE, BfR, INSERM, UU-IRAS, UAntwerpen, UU, UIBK, UFZ).

• **P5.2.1.c_Y1_EDThDisruption_DTU**

Most partners (some will start only in Y2 or are in the phase of hiring personnel) have initiated their activities. After the ED-Thyroid kickoff meeting (3 June), a mapping of the activities of the different groups to the existing Thyroid Hormone System Disruption (THSD) AOP network has been established by individual project partners responding to activity map created by UAntwerpen (needed for AD5.3). Other work done so far includes the planning of the *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies as well as the multi-organ and cross-species transcriptomics studies, exploration of data sets relevant for QSAR-modelling (e.g. TTR), molecular docking simulations of human Thyroid hormone Receptor beta (hTRb) agonists and antagonists, characterisation of the evolutionary conservation of the Thyroid Hormone System (THS) axis in relation to invertebrates and non-mammalian vertebrates, literature review to extrapolate THSD from fish/amphibians to mammals/humans based on the existing cross-species AOP network. The proposal to publish the 'ED-Thyroid project' for publication in a Special Topic in Frontiers in Toxicology has been accepted and writing is ongoing (DTU, VUB, BfR, SDU, UAntwerpen, UFZ, VUA, ISCII, INSERM).

• **P5.2.1.d_Y1_Immunotox_INSERM**

The activities of partners have been organised in three groups: respiratory sensitisation (MUI, NPHC, RIVM), immunosuppression (INSERM, NIPH, INSA, LIH) and NAM development (IRAS, UL-FFA, INSA, UFZ, WFSR), reflecting different key events in immunotoxicity. This organisation is in line with that of Activity 5.3.2 on AOP development, thus ensuring coherent work across the two activities. Activities related to the set-up of *in vitro* systems that allow the assay of key events in the immune

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system function or dysfunction have been initiated. Experimental models have been defined, discussed by all partners in dedicated workshops and SOPs are under preparation (needed for AD5.3). We had 5 workshops for the full projects (4th July, 30th August, 8th Sept, 12th Oct, 5th Dec 2022), each one consisting in presentations and discussions by the different partners. Each workshop lasts 2h at least. In addition to the global projects meetings, each subgroup (response sensitization, immunosuppression, NAM development in immune system) had more targeted meetings on a regular basis. Chemicals to be used in each assay have been identified and they correspond either to model chemicals or the priority chemicals identified in WP5. As soon as suppliers will be identified, chemicals will be purchased and experiments will start.

- **P5.2.1.e_Y1_Neurotox_UFZ_IUF_UU**

Regulatory testing for acute neurotoxicity (ANT) or developmental neurotoxicity (DNT) is currently performed in mammals (OECD TG #424, 426). We seek to develop, evaluate and implement new approach methods (NAMs) for DNT or ANT that, based on the mode of action of toxicants, inform on safe chemical concentrations. In WP5.1, established DNT/ANT assays with sufficient readiness will be used for chemical testing (i.e., BPA analogs, mycotoxins, PFAS). P 5.2.1 We focuses explicitly on the development of new assays that fill critical gaps in the existing DNT/ANT *in vitro* test batteries (IVB). Action 1 comprises the development of NAMs for detection of ANT. In the reporting period, we collected information on the partners' acute neurotoxicity (ANT) assays, assay readiness levels and ANT modes of action. Action 2 seeks to fill gaps in the existing DNT *in vitro* test battery (DNT IVB). Here, we collected information on the partners' DNT assays and readiness levels. The assay list is being used to design a comparative study on performance, sensitivity, specificity and redundancy of DNT test methods. With regard to chemical selection, candidate model compound lists from consortium member projects and via interaction with ASPIS cluster EU projects have been assembled and a semi-automatic workflow was prepared to compile candidate compounds with physico-chemical, structural and toxicological properties. Action 3 aims to develop zebrafish assays to complement DNT and ANT IVBs. In the reporting period, we collected information on the partners' zebrafish ANT/DNT assays and assay readiness levels. We took a key decision that, as the zebrafish light/dark transition test is undergoing an OECD ring study, P5.2.1e will focus on the development, evaluation, and use of novel DNT/ANT zebrafish assays. Novel endpoints include: learning, memory, startle response, social interaction, place preference, and anxiety-like behavior, and neuroendocrine system plasticity. The same chemical selection criteria applied to Action 2 will be used here (INSERM-UBX, UU, NIPH, IUF, UKON, RIVM, UFZ, ISCIII, TiHo, AIT, NMBU).

- A5.2.2 Innovative methods and tools for toxicity testing and modelling for Environmental Toxicology / Ecotoxicology

This activity has been developed during Y1 jointly with **P5.1.2.b_Y1_BPAalternatives_BPI_MU**, since both focus in the environmental aspect.

The project has two main activities, one focuses on filling data gaps (5.1.2) and another one on NAMs development (5.2.2). The two activities have in common to study BPA alternatives on environment.

Activity 5.2.2 is focused on the development of the new methodologies that cover a broad spectrum of approaches from *in silico* to *in vivo* and the spectrum of studied endpoints (e.g., neurotoxicity, oxidative stress, immunity, development, reproduction, behavioral, metabolisms and endocrine disruption among others). During Y1, partners' information on NAMs were collected and discussed to identify synergies and overlaps. In addition, to identify BPA alternatives that will be suitable for the development of specific NAMs, experts have been working on a review summarising the toxicity of the BPA alternatives

identified from the BPA alternatives priority list (AD5.1). A joint meeting with Activities 5.1.1. & 5.1.2 was held, where the content and contributions of the review were discussed (11/2022). The meeting served also as a platform where 5.2.2. partners propose sophisticated studies to be conducted in years 2 and 3. In parallel, 5.2.2. is involved in an cross-task activity initiated by WP6: discussions and meetings around environment to identify synergies and overlaps.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD5.3	List of first assays to be developed for prioritised endpoints	DTU FOOD/VUB/MU	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

The main difficulties relate to very short time that was requested to fill all necessary forms (updates of the project description, budget construction, annual summary report, annual work plan, etc.). In many cases TLs had limited chances to collect all information from all partners, specifically on cases where new information was required in forms that were available to TLs in short time before submission. For some partners, delays in contract finalisation and hence money transfer from GS to AE occur, delaying the process of hiring personnel and postponing the planned experimental work.

1.5.3. Task 5.3. Quantitative systems toxicology and development of new AOPs

Leader: UL-LACDR (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), INSERM (FR), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE)

Participants:

Activity 5.3.1: AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), KIT (DE), MUI (AT), NIPH (NO), NPHC (HU), Sciensano (BE), UFZ (DE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIABDN (UK), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.3.2: ACES/SU(SE), AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BfG (DE), BPI (EL), DTU (DK), IISPV (ES), INSERM (FR), IRSN (FR), ISS (IT), KI (SE), KIT (DE), KU-Leuven (BE), MUI (AT), NILU (NO), NIPH (NO), NPHC (HU), Sciensano (BE), SDU (DK), UAntwerpen (BE), UGent (BE), UG-PL (PL), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UMIL (IT), UNIVIE (AT), WSFR (NL)

Activity 5.3.3: ANSES (FR), ETHZ (CZ), Fraunhofer-ITEM (DE), IISPV (ES), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISCIII (ES), ISS (IT), NVI (NO), UHC (DE), UIBK (AT), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT); WR (NL), WU-TOX (NL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: i) Establishing different core or extended groups relevant for the activity of this task: omics, Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs), bioinformatics, effect markers, PBTK, *in vivo/in vitro* mode of action; ii) establishing an inventory and mapping available knowledge, reference *in vivo*/human datasets, activities and models in systems biology, PBTK and AOP frameworks and prioritising additional studies and iii) initiating studies to characterise coreregulated gene networks, for already published AOPs (to make them quantitative) and linking chemicals to available AOPs, linking

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omics data to human physiopathology, generating high quality ADME data and ultimately building new AOPs.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

- A5.3.1 Prioritised NAM-based mechanistic hazard characterisation and A5.3.3 Translation to human pathophysiology (Systems toxicology approaches for mechanism-based chemical safety assessment).

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

These two activities were combined in a single project for coherence purposes:

- **P5.3.1.a_Y1_SystemsToxicology_UL-LACDR:** In Y1, the project was further refined and several actions were defined involving different sets of partners. The actions are: to agree on data set recovery and systems toxicology tooling, coupled with a workshop on data requirement for systems toxicology; to identify and integrate Mode of Action (MoA) information using various data sources and to establish novel reference transcriptomics data sets for prioritised NAMs; to establish bioinformatics tools for systems toxicology-based hazard characterisation; to support human relevance by integrating human omics data sets, filling gaps in human pathophysiology using datasets from existing biobanks; to correlate in vitro and in vivo data on MoA with human data; to develop case studies; work on these objectives started in Y1 and will be further developed in Y2.
- A5.3.2 AOP development based on integration

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P5.3.2.a_Y1_AOPDevelopment_INSERM**
Different groups related to prioritised outcomes were constituted during Y1: a core group (CG) with expertise in methods for AOP development; three specialty groups (SG1: immunotoxicity and NGTxC; SG2: endocrine disruption; SG3: neurotoxicity) and an effect markers group. The groups started working by inventorying available methods, AOPs and effect markers in each topic. The CG further developed tools linking chemicals to AOP events and planned a workshop with international institutions involved in AOP development to support coordination (first trimester 2023).
- A5.3.4 PBTK models and quantitative systems toxicology

Projects progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK models and quantitative systems toxicology_Fraunhofer**
In Y1, four different groups were established to develop a strategy for data recovery and development of case studies to address knowledge as well as conceptual gaps in IVIVE-PBK models. By this activity we will ensure that the PBK models developed in this project will be useful for the development of quantitative AOPs (a close link to 5.3.2) and also for in vitro to in vivo extrapolations (a close link to WP 6.1). Until end of 2022, a knowledge and data gap analysis are performed to develop case studies that specifically address these.
The core group comprises experts in PBK modelling and/or in vitro ADME models (P5.3.4.a_Y1_PBK_Kinetics_Fraunhofer). It coordinates the selection of case study compounds

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according to the identified data and conceptual knowledge gaps. The core group also coordinates the cooperation with WP 5.3.2 and WP6 to generate a harmonised framework for kinetic modelling. For this purpose, regular meetings are planned, once the case studies have started and results can be discussed (the first early 2023). The core groups will further reach out to other international organisations/projects driving PBK modelling, a workshop is planned for the second or third trimester in 2023.

Three specialty groups (SGs) addressing PBK model approaches for the oral, or the inhalation route of exposure as well as for system toxicology have been built. An initial set of case studies has been defined. Each case study is led by one PBK modeller and one in vitro ADME expert. The planned case studies will address: impact of the human microbiome on xenobiotic metabolism and uptake; impact of isoform specific metabolism; tiered testing approach to address in vitro ADME models for inhalation exposure; PBK models for priority compounds i) Alternaria toxins; ii) Mycotoxins; iii) Enniatins; iv) BPA alternatives; iv) PFAS. Selection criteria for case study compounds include the availability of high quality in vivo ADME studies, which can be used to quantify the uncertainty of the obtained models.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD5.4	Inventory of omics data, biochemical data, other relevant readouts in public domain repositories for all PARC selected adverse outcomes	UL-LACDR./SCI ENSANO/INS ERM/Fraunhofer	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD5.5	Inventory of the available (networks of) AOPs, prioritisation and establishment of the framework for further development in PARC	UL-LACDR./SCI ENSANO/INS ERM/Fraunhofer	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD5.6	PARC Coordination Team	UL-LACDR./SCI ENSANO/INS ERM/Fraunhofer	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD5.7	Draft strategy for the development of bioinformatics tools that are needed to link omics data and other mechanistic information to human relevant disease mechanisms	UL-LACDR./SCI ENSANO/INS ERM/Fraunhofer	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problems encountered.

1.6. Work package 6¹. Innovation in RA

1.6.1. Task 6.1. Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment of Chemicals

Leader: SCIENSANO (BE), UL-LACDR (NL)

Participants: AUTH (EL); BPI (EL); DTU FOOD (DK); UAVR (PT); ENSP (PT); Fraunhofer (DE); IISPV (ES); IfADo (DE); INERIS (FR); INRAE (FR); INSERM (FR); IRFM (IT); IRSN (FR); ISS (IT); KI (SE); KWR (NL); LIST (LU); MOH-CY/SGL (CY); MU (CZ); MUI (AT); NILU (NO); NIPH (NO); UOB (UK); UKHSA (UK); UKCEH (UK); UG-PL (PL); RIVM (NL); SDU (DK); STAMI (NO); UAntwerpen (BE); UGent (BE); UU-IRAS (NL); VUB (BE); WR (NL); WU-TOX (NL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing quantitative networks of Adverse Outcome Pathways (AOPs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity, to assess their human relevance and to identify associated NAMs. Based on this work, development of regulatory relevant Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity will be initiated, in close collaboration with relevant stakeholders. Dedicated case studies to evaluate the IATAs will be designed.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

The projects described below are aimed at the development of IATAs for three different health effects, *i.e.* genotoxicity, endocrine disruption and liver toxicity. In conjunction, a workflow for the assessment of human relevance is being developed. Since a similar stepwise approach is used for each of these projects, we here report the work done for the four projects together. Each of the four projects covers work related to A6.1.1, A6.1.2, and A6.1.3. Therefore, there are no separate projects for the different activities within T6.1.

- A6.1.1: Development of IATAs for regulatory purposes

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

As a first step the partners involved in T6.1 discussed together per project whether the objectives and/or approaches described needed refinement. Based on the outcomes of the discussions held, the project descriptions (including specification of the contribution of each partner) were updated. In essence, the objectives remained the same for all four projects.

For each project, two partners volunteered and were approved as project leads. Under their coordination, a first overview of useful AOPs, published in the AOP-Wiki and/or scientific literature, has been created for each of the health effects. This overview, developed in close collaboration with WP5, will be further refined and subsequently used for the development of AOP networks (to be reported in AD5.5 in M12). Additionally, valuable NAMs (*in silico*/computational tools and *in vitro* test methods) for the different health effects addressed have been identified. A first draft of the different IATAs is under development. To ensure a common understanding of the IATA concept and associated terminology, a core team on IATAs has been established. This team, involving all partners in T6.1, meets regularly to discuss the

¹ In the AWPY1, the work description for WP6 was mainly described by task. The description of the work is more detailed in the ASRY1 with a division of the work by activity and projects according to the AWPY1 SRIA

IATA concept, possible approaches for the development of an IATA and issues encountered. Furthermore, together with T8.3 partners, a core team on quantitative AOPs has been formed.

- **P6.1.1.a_Y1_HumanRelevance_RIVM:** The project, led by RIVM and AUTH, aims to establish a workflow for the assessment of human relevance of AOPs and the relevance of NAMs related to the key events or key event relationships of the pathway under study. A project team has been established and recurring meetings have been planned and held. The existing framework developed by WHO/IPCS together with the draft workflow developed by RIVM was discussed by the project team. Additionally, an overview of valuable approaches for weight of evidence assessment and uncertainty analysis is being developed. This is done in close collaboration with WP7.
- **P6.1.1.b_Y1_IATA_ED_UAntwerpen:** The project, led by UAntwerpen and UKHSA, aims to develop IATAs for identifying endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) both in a human and environmental health context. A project team has been established and recurring meetings have been planned and held. Because of the ample interest in this topic by different consortium partners, it was decided to focus not only on thyroid effects. Based on the current knowledge and expertise and NAMs available, it was decided to also develop an IATA for anti-androgenic effects. An overview of relevant AOPs is being created and potentially useful NAMs are being identified. All the work done is carried out by building on ongoing work performed in the context of the EURION cluster, at OECD and the JRC. Also, opportunities for collaboration with the French non-profit association PEPPER are being explored.
- **P6.1.1.c_Y1_IATA_GENTOX_Sciensano:** The project, led by Sciensano and INRAE, aims to develop an IATA for genetic toxicity, one of the health effects prioritized in the EU Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability. Moreover, various non-animal tools for the identification of genotoxic effects are available, and some of them have been used for regulatory purposes for some time now. A project team has been established and recurring meetings have been planned and held. An overview of relevant AOPs is being created. For this, a close collaboration with the Genetic Toxicology Technical Committee of HESI (Health and Environmental Sciences Institute) has been set up, to ensure that work is not duplicated and recent insights in the field are shared and discussed.
- **P6.1.1.d_Y1_IATA_STOT_UL-LACDR:** The project, led by UL-LACDR, aims to develop an IATA for liver toxicity, with an initial focus on liver fibrosis. A project team has been established and recurring meetings have been planned and held. An overview of relevant AOPs is being created. Furthermore, a close collaboration with projects from the ASPIS cluster, i.e. RISK-HUNT3R and ONTOX, is being established, to take advantage of ongoing activities in those project, such as the development of qAOPs.

➤ A6.1.2: Evaluation of IATAs through case studies

No project submitted at present.

The IATAs listed in A6.1.1 will be developed through various cycles of optimisation; (interim) evaluations will be conducted through case studies. For the first round of case studies, criteria for suitable substances are being developed and candidate substances have been identified. The design of the case studies is being discussed in both the respective project teams and the core team on IATAs. Additionally, meetings with T5.3 have been scheduled to discuss how to best achieve incorporation of PBK modelling results in the IATA case studies. Where feasible, the case studies for specific IATAs will be linked to case studies for the workflow for assessment of human relevance. A description of the

case studies to be conducted, for IATAs as well as human relevance assessment, will be reported as milestone in M12.

➤ A6.1.3: Stakeholder engagement

No project submitted at present.

The work done in Task 6.1 is closely related to regulatory risk assessment. Therefore, active involvement of regulatory partners is crucial to ensure that the outcomes will meet regulatory needs. Following presentation of the T6.1 projects in the WP6 workshop held on 15-16 September in Bilthoven, dedicated meetings with EFSA, ECHA, JRC, and SCCS have been planned to discuss in more detail how to achieve active regulatory involvement in a consistent manner. Collaborations with other stakeholders are being explored, including OECD (all projects), and the World Health Organization and ILMERAC (International Liaison group on Methods for Risk Assessment of Chemicals in food) for human relevance. All the work in A6.1.3 is performed in close collaboration with WPs 2 and 3.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS15 (former AD6.2)	Case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs designed	SCIENSANO/UL-LACDR	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD6.1	Strategy document on IATA for more complex endpoints	SCIENSANO/UL-LACDR	31/10/2023 (M18) instead of 28/02/2023 (M10)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

Due to the complexity of PARC, it took more time than anticipated to bring all partners involved at the same level of understanding. Consequently, to avoid unnecessary spending of capacity, appointment of suitable personnel was somewhat delayed (although this may vary across partners) and there have been delays in kicking off the work. We envision that the delayed work will be partly carried out in the remainder of the first year and partly in the second year of PARC.

The additional deliverable AD6.1 ‘Strategy document on IATAs for more complex endpoints’ is anticipated to be achieved in M18 instead of M10. The justification for the delay is two-fold: firstly, due to the complexity of PARC the start of the actual work has been somewhat delayed. Secondly, having a better insight into the different tasks and activities planned in PARC, we decided to change our approach. We will develop the strategy for IATAs for more complex endpoints through a series of (online) workshops, to be held in the first six months of 2023. For this, we will closely collaborate with other WPs, especially WPs 2, 3 and 5. In these workshops, a broad selection of PARC partners and stakeholders, including representatives of related initiatives, will participate.

Moreover, we propose to change AD6.2 ‘Report on case studies for interim evaluation of IATAs’ (M12) into a milestone MS15, to be achieved at M12. The milestone will consist of a brief description of the

case studies envisaged for the four projects in task 6.1. The design and progress of the case studies themselves will be reported in an AD in year 2 (which will be listed as such in AWP Y2).

1.6.2. Task 6.2. Integrative exposure and risk assessment

Leader: ANSES (FR), VITO (BE)

Participants: AU (DK), AUTH (EL), BPI (EL), CSTB (FR), DTU FOOD (DK), EFSA (IT), EHESP (FR), ENSP (PT), FINBA (ES), TTL (FI), FMUL (PT), FOPH (CH), Fraunhofer (DE), GEoSZ (SI), ICPS (IT), CSIC (ES), IISPV (ES), KI (SE), INERIS (FR), INRAE (FR), INRS (FR), INSA (PT), IRFM (IT), ISCIII (ES), ISSeP (BE), IUSS (IT), IVL (SE), KWR (NL), LNS (LU), MOH-CY/SGL (CY), MU (CZ), NIJZ (SI), NIOM (PL), NIPH (NO), NLZOH (SI), OI (SI), ONIRIS (FR), RIVM (NL), RUMC (NL), SCIENSANO (BE), SECO (CH), SLU (SE), STAMI (NO), TNO (NL), UAVR (PT), UBA (DE), UGR (ES), UG-PL (PL), UNIPD (IT), UNISANTE (CH), USI (CH), UU-IRAS (NL), WR (NL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing innovative methods, tools and concepts and performing integrative risk and health impact assessments based on internal and external exposure of humans exposed to single chemicals and mixtures from multiple sources and routes for different living environments (including workplace).

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

Task 6.2 is divided in eight projects that are interconnected aiming to improve integrated risk assessment. These projects are using human biomonitoring data and data and models for predictive risk assessment as currently in practice. The projects will contribute to the identification of the sources of exposure and the health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and mixtures thereof. For improving integrated risk assessment, two projects on aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes of exposure are launched. Inventories are made of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population and for workers in the occupational settings. For understanding how a chemical inserts its health effect, information or data describing the adsorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion of a chemical in a human body is relevant. Therefore, a project on the refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment and mixtures risk assessment based on HBM data started. Initial work is launched on a strategy to perform risk assessment of mixtures organised into 3 groups of experts working on 1) integration of HBM exposure data, 2) hazard assessment and grouping chemicals into mixture assessment groups according to international guidance documents from the OECD and EFSA, and 3) improved kinetic models to optimize risk assessment based on HBM data. The kinetic models will bridge internal measures based on HBM data, as generated in HBM4EU and WP4 of PARC, with external exposure assessment results as performed by the European or national Agencies. For better understanding co-exposure of chemicals, two approaches for the identification of mixtures of chemicals are developed and programmed in the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) software. This in close cooperation with task 8.3 and EFSA endorsing the MCRA software for regulatory implementation of mixtures of pesticides according to the legal requirements described in the Pesticide Regulation. Four related task 6.2 projects started to better understand the health impact of exposure to hazardous chemicals and mixtures thereof. These projects started work on organizing data, developing methods for health impact assessment and understanding the associated uncertainties and how the uncertainties can be reduced. Once these methods are mature, it will facilitate to compare risk assessment results overtime.

- A6.2.1 Aggregated exposure assessment from multiple sources and routes for general population and workers

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Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

This activity includes two projects.

In **P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO**, inventories have been made of realistic source-to-dose models for the general population to assess (i) direct exposure to chemicals released from consumer products and materials, and (ii) direct and indirect exposure via release and transfer from the environment. Gaps (models and data), priority chemicals, products, and environmental sources for the project were defined. First steps were taken to generate a mechanistic understanding of source-to-dose exposure and to translate this into a conceptual model. The inventory of existing data to parametrise the conceptual model was initiated.

- In **P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_ANSES**, the inventory of occupational and general life models to estimate exposure from various sources and routes of exposure has been started on the basis of the previous works initiated by the International Society of Exposure Science (ISES) and the Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD). The different data sources which can be used to feed the exposure models (occupational and general life) were also identified. Based on the definition of relevant criteria and starting from the proposed case studies in the project working plan, a deeper investigation of the available data has been started to study the feasibility of the case studies which will start the second year of the project. Partners were organised in project working groups with common interest in case studies. Also, the design of the strategy to assess aggregate exposure from various living environments has been started.
- A6.2.2 Modelling exposure through life

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPk_INERIS: this project consists in the refinement and development of PBPK models for human risk assessment and mixtures risk assessment (in collaboration with the activity 6.2.3. The aim of the first project is to provide PBPK models that address the sensitivity of different population sub-groups, the aggregation of multiple exposure routes, and the interpretation of HBM data and the mixtures of chemicals. Several prioritised chemical families are studied: PFAS, pesticides, metals, bisphenols and mycotoxins. The first step was to inventory the human PBPK models available that were published or developed by partners since the review done in the HBM4EU project in 2019. For all chemical families, at least one new model was identified. The main characteristics of the models were gathered in a database (e.g., populations, the exposure and elimination routes, the organs included, the language code). Each new model is described using the roadmap established in the HBM4EU project. Several pProject working groups gathering few partners were defined: one for each family, and one on the parametrisation of the physiology and anatomy and their dynamic evolution through life (e.g., the ontogeny of enzyme activities, transporters, etc.). This work will be reported in the deliverable AD6.5 (Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life) due at M12. Four meetings for this project were organised in 2022 (May, July, October, and December).

- A6.2.3 Mixture exposure and risk assessment

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM**:

In P6.2.3.a_Y1_RealLifeMixtures_RIVM, we have started to develop a strategy to perform risk assessment for mixtures observed in real-life. This is based on HBM data. The work is organised into three groups of experts working on:

1. exposure assessment based on HBM studies;
2. hazard data and grouping of chemicals into mixture assessment groups following international guidance of OECD and EFSA;
3. kinetic conversion of internal and external exposure doses.

The experts started work on five case studies addressing chemicals and effects from the PARC prioritization process. The case studies are:

- pesticides causing brain and/or erythrocyte AChE inhibition (CAG-NAN);
- pesticides causing functional alterations of the motor division (CAG-NAM);
- PFAS and immune effect;
- heavy metals and kidney effects;
- chemicals from different chemical families affecting the nervous system during development of an individual (e.g. IQ-loss);
- mycotoxins and immune and haematological effects.

We organised and summarised the HBM data from more than 50 HBM studies including the aligned studies from the HBM4EU project and studies from partners that did not participate in the HBM4EU aligned studies. Statistical methods will be applied to selected HBM studies to identify and prioritised real-life mixtures. Two statistical methods regarding the identification of co-exposure of chemicals forming a mixture are now implemented in the Monte Carlo Risk Assessment (MCRA) software, which is the software in connection to some models from the integrated model platform in task 8.3, that will be used in this project.

For the prioritised chemical families and effects, we started to organise the information needed for hazard input data such as effect specific HBM-GV, effect specific Relative Potency Factors (RPFs) of the prioritised chemicals observed in the HBM studies.

For the prioritized chemicals and effects a PBPK model inventory is being made. This is complementary to the one done in the project (P6.2.2.a_Y1_PBPK_INERIS). The inventory aims to identify missing PBPK models for chemicals in the studied mixtures. Furthermore literature research was performed for missing kinetic parameters and to data is gathered for the model parametrization. A comparison of the model predictions obtained with generic vs. substance-specific models (acute and chronic exposure) was carried out to determine whether or not the generic model has similar performance than the specific-substance ones. In close cooperation with PARC task 8.3, the statistical methods and PBPK model parameters are being programmed into the MCRA and other related software packages such as Integra as an interoperable model platform.

The project relies on input data and will generate output data. The appointed data champions of the project and the developers of the software work in close cooperation with the project leaders (ANSES and RIVM) and WP7 leaders to align data and tools for implementation of mixture risk assessment. Harmonized coding and/or formatting of input data is partly achieved. This project has provided training and will be further optimise training for stakeholders in close cooperation with PARC task 9.4.

During the WP6 workshop we engaged risk managers. As a follow-up of that workshop we are discussing progress with dedicated groups of DG SANTE and EFSA with a focus on how risk managers can benefit from task 6.2 results. This is complementary to (and in synergy with) ongoing regulatory

discussion between EFSA, RIVM, ANSES, BfR, EC-JRC and DG SANTE on regulatory implementation of dietary mixture risk assessment of pesticides.

➤ A6.2.4 Human health impact assessment and risk indicators

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- In **P6.2.4.a_Y1_HIADDataAvailability_VITO**, a concise inventory was made of health impact assessments conducted for PARC priority chemicals and mixtures, based on expertise available among partners and literature search. Available external and internal exposure data and exposure-effect functions were collected as well and an overview of availability, quality and accessibility of European and national health data registries was made. First steps were made to evaluate possibilities to fill data gaps via in-silico modelling of exposures, derivation of population-specific exposures and spatio-temporal and interindividual variations, and establishment of exposure-effect associations by linking exposure, lifestyle, geographical, SES, and health status data, comparing multiple time frames, regions and populations.
- **P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS** generated an inventory of methodologies and frameworks (including a glossary of definitions) for health impact assessment and environmental burden of disease calculations and associated uncertainties, which will form the basis for identification and planning of methodological improvements to be addressed in PARC.
- **P6.2.4.c_Y1_HIACaseStudies_UU-IRAS** started with definition of a framework to complete the first activities of the project, including a set of criteria for prioritisation of case studies to start in year 2, which were discussed with stakeholders, followed by a proof of concept in which the criteria were applied and a long list of case studies was proposed.
- In **P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO**, an inventory of existing types of risk and health impact indicators based on expertise available among partners, literature search, communication materials of (inter)national organisations, and stakeholder input (JRC and EEA for indicators related to the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability and Farm to Fork Strategy). Together with the case study prioritisation, this will form the basis for a proposal for indicator development from year 2 onwards.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD6.3	Roadmap on aggregated exposure strategy through different living environments sources and routes	UNISANTE/ANSES	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD6.4	Inventory of PBK models for assessing the internal exposure through life and for in-vitro-to-in-vivo extrapolation	INERIS/AUTH	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
AD6.5	Report describing co-occurrence probabilities of chemicals forming real life mixtures of the selected HBM studies across Europe and	RIVM/ANSES	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

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	overview of the kinetic and grouping aspects of prioritised mixtures				
AD6.6	Inventory of existing HIA, exposure and exposure-effect data for chemicals prioritised in PARC	VITO/UU	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

Some part of the work of the projects P6.2.1.a_Y1_SourcetoDose_VITO, P6.2.1.b_Y1_Aggregate_Anse, P6.2.4.b_Y1_HIAMethod_UU-IRAS and P6.2.4.d_Y1_HIAIndicators_VITO and some partners have started later because of financial and recruitment problems to involve staff to help leaders work on the projects.

1.6.3. Task 6.3. Review of risk assessment methodologies

Leader: SU (SE), BPI (EL)

Participants: UCL (UK), INSA (PT), EAA (AT), EAWAG (CH), TTL (FI), FOEN (CH), INERIS (FR), INSERM (FR), IRFM (IT), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), LSMU (LT), MUI (AT), REGIONH (DK), RSU (LV), SCIENSANO (BE), STAMI (NO), SYKE (FI), UBA (DE), ULUND (SE), VUB (BE), UNIBAS (CH), KEMI (SE)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Initiating case studies reviewing selected methodologies and approaches for regulatory RA

➤ A6.3.1 Substance and effect specific reviews

Under the activity, two projects have been initiated: Case studies reviewing substance-specific RA depending on intended use (P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU) and Case studies reviewing effect-specific RA (P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI).

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- In **P6.3.1.a_Y1_SubstanceRA_SU**, three reviews (case studies) of substance-specific assessments depending on intended use have been initiated. The case studies have been designed to evaluate and understand differences and similarities, and subsequent implications, across legislations. (SU, UCL, SCIENSANO, IRFM, KI)
- **P6.3.1.a_Y1_CS12_MethodOSOA_SU**: A prioritisation and selection of substances for a case study on risk assessment processes, including significant differences between processes, strengths of the current system(s), and potential gaps, overlaps, or inefficiencies has been initiated.
- **P6.3.1.a_Y1_CS13_PlasticizersRA_UCL**: A mapping of known uses and corresponding legislations for selected plastic additives have been initiated, including comparisons of e.g., testing requirements, use and availability of modelling tools, weight-of-evidence approaches, and derivation of safety thresholds. Peer-reviewed publications are expected to be drafted during the year 2 of PARC.

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- **P6.3.1.a_Y1_CS14_BiocidesRA_SU:** A review on the regulation and assessment of biocides when used in cosmetic products compared to biocidal products has been initiated, including how scientific data is used and consequences of the potential differences in regulation and risk assessment.
- In **P6.3.1.b_Y1_EffectRA_BPI**, six reviews of effect-specific assessments have been initiated, including sensitisation and developmental neurotoxicity as well as use of non-animal methods for identification of endocrine disruption, genotoxicity, and carcinogenicity. (REGIONH, STAMI, SU, IRFM, UNIBAS, VUB, ISS, NILU, INSA, BPI, KI, INSERM, INERIS, EAA, UBA)
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS9_SKINSENSIRISK_REGIONH:** A mapping of current practices under different regulations concerning risk assessment of skin sensitizer, including the scientific basis, has been initiated. A questionnaire has been sent to national and EU authorities, industry, and other stakeholders.
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS10_ED-cosmetics_VUB:** A critical analysis of SCCS risk assessments for a selection of the 14 high priority ED cosmetic substances (Group A), including methodology, NAMs, and alternative strategies (NGRA), has been initiated. Contacts with Cosmetics Europe and SCCS.
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS11_GenotoxCarc_ISS:** A mapping of existing documentation, regulations, and related guidelines as well as a review of the methodologies and practices employed under different regulatory frameworks related to genotoxicity and carcinogenicity assessment has been initiated.
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS15_DNT_SU:** An evaluation of conclusions drawn in guideline-compliant developmental neurotoxicity studies has been initiated, with a focus on data availability and data collection, also including if a uniform statistical analysis can identify previously unreported effects.
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS17_ED-in vitro_BPI:** Identification and prioritisation of end-points relevant for the assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals has been performed. Literature and database search for the identification of available *in vitro* test methods assessing the prioritised endpoints has been initiated. Interaction with and implementation of results and methods from the EURION cluster.
- **P6.3.1.b_Y1_CS18_ED-classes_BPI:** Identification of available *in vitro* test methods, *in silico* models/tools and read-across approaches relevant for the assessment of endocrine disrupting chemicals with regard to androgen, estrogen, steroidogenesis and thyroid modalities has been initiated. Interaction with and implementation of results and methods from the EURION cluster.

➤ A6.3.2 Use of tools, criteria, and methods

Under the activity, one project has been initiated: Case studies reviewing tools, criteria, and methods used in regulatory RA (P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU).

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- In **P6.3.2.a_Y1_ToolsRA_SU**, eight reviews on the use of tools, criteria, and methods in regulatory RA have been initiated, including general aspects such as application of risk-based benchmarks and uncertainty analysis as well as aspects related to occupational RA and ERA. (SYKE, ISSeP, SU, STAMI, UBA, JSI, UCL, TTL, KI, RSU, INERIS, MUI, KEMI, ULUND, BPI, LSMU, EAWAG, FOEN)

- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS1_CARBSYKE**: A survey on risk-based decision benchmarks considered in risk assessment methodologies under different EU regulatory frameworks has been initiated. The scope and methodology have been defined and relevant data compilation is in progress.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS2_RiskReduction_SU**: A literature review for the identification of available methods on how to evaluate the effectiveness of risk assessment for risk reduction has been initiated.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS6_SusChemControl_MUI**: The development of a hierarchical mindmap has been initiated with the purpose to identify options beyond AOP, NAM and IATA development for a sustainable regulation of chemicals.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS16_UncertaintyRA_ULUND**: The description of generic components of uncertainty analyses for common and relevant types of assessment has been initiated. Collection of information on practical challenges through a questionnaire with follow up interviews has been initiated.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS7_REGPREP_EAWAG**: A review regarding aquatic and sediment RA has been initiated, including identification of substances and mapping of topics for the identification of similarities and differences, and areas requiring further analysis of several different effect values.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS4_SecPoisoning_INERIS**: A review of current practices applied for secondary poisoning assessment across several regulatory frameworks has been initiated. Particular consideration has been made on the regular review for update of ECHA's chemical safety assessment and reporting tool (Chesar) and European Union System for the Evaluation of Substances (EUSES) under REACH.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS8_OccupReproDev_KI**: A review of the EU and member state occupational exposure limits for reproductive toxicants 1A or 1B has been initiated. The review includes comparisons of key decisions in the hazard assessments, comparisons to other regulatory areas including REACH.
- **P6.3.2.a_Y1_CS3_WorkplaceRA_TTL**: A review on the existing regulatory documents has been initiated with the purpose to identify case examples on the different options to regulate occupational chemical exposure either under OSH, REACH or both.

Joint WP6 workshop

A workshop with WP and task leaders, partners, and relevant stakeholders was organised at RIVM, Bilthoven, The Netherlands, on September 15-16, 2022. During day one the WP6 tasks presented their objectives, approaches, and projects. The second day was dedicated to presentations by stakeholders on priorities and regulatory needs as well as guided discussions on how WP6 can contribute to addressing the needs. Presentations were given by DG Sante, DG ENV, JRC, EFSA, ECHA and SCCS. The Coordination team as well as other PARC WPs were represented at the workshop. (KEMI, RIVM, all WP6 partners).

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

Not applicable

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

One case study (12 PMs) planned to be initiated during the period was withdrawn before the start of PARC. This has been communicated to the PARC Coordinator.

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1.6.4. Task 6.4. Transposing results to regulatory risk assessment methodologies

Leader: AGES (AT), UNIBAS (CH)

Participants: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), OFB (FR), EAA (AT), AGES (AT), MU (CZ), AU (DK), REGIONH-GR (DK), UT (EE), EFSA (EU), SYKE (FI), Tukes (FI), UBA (DE), UFZ (DE), UKOLD (DE), USO (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), UI (IS), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), LSMU (LT), VUA (NL), NIPH (NO), STAMI (NO), NIVA (NO), NIOM (PL), IEP-NRI (PL), UG-PL (PL), INSA (PT), ENSP (PT), UC (PT), UAVR (PT), ISCHII (ES), UCLM (SI), UGOT (SE), ULUND (SE), RISE (SE), KEMI (SE), SLU (SE), AGROSCOPE (CH), EAWAG (CH), FOEN (CH), UNIBAS (CH), BUL (UK), UKCEH (UK), UOB (UK), BPI (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Laying the groundwork for the development of efficient and protective regulatory RA and underpinning development of regulations through stakeholder workshops, review of knowledge, landscaping exercises, action plan developments and case studies which will inform the decisions on how (and which) approaches should be developed

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

- A6.4.1. Develop regulatory relevant approaches and methods for chemical mixtures

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P6.4.1.a_Y1_CS1_BRUNEL_UGot** aims to perform a systematic comparative evaluation of current mixture tools (and those that are currently under development or might be developed within PARC). The mixture tools will be compared regarding their practicability, effectiveness and efficiency, level of protection, feasibility, applications domain and data demands. The first step was to complement the recent literature reviews on the current approaches related to mixtures with information on the current regulatory practices in order to identify the main gaps and needs and possible ways forwards across regulations. Further an overview of the different algorithms for estimating the MAF was made. A survey for collecting data through interviews on current assessment practices and data availabilities is in the initiation phase. A joint discussion with Project leaders of P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ and some partners (EAWAG/UBA/UKCEH) and a separate discussion with AGES about case studies for further exploring the MAF (useability, size) took place at the WP 6 Workshop in Bilthoven, in the Netherlands on September 15-16 2022 .
- In **P6.4.1.b_Y1_CS2_UFZ** the use of new approach methods (NAMs) i.e., bioanalytical methods for untargeted exposure detection and hazard identification in conjunction with chemical screening data, to deal with unknown mixtures will be compared with mixture risk assessment methods relying on component-based standard toxicity information. Monitoring information based on non-target chemical and bioanalytical methods will be utilised to define unknown mixture exposures. As a first step, a data research and retrieval were performed to build a reference background mixture for European wastewater treatment plant effluents based on monitoring and NAM data including initial data analyses and identification of data gaps. Further, a curation of NORMAN monitoring database for further analyses of compound co-occurrence and mixture heterogeneity across Europe with focus on chemicals regulated under REACH was done. Besides the research, several discussions about this project took place as a

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joint discussion and case study identification with UFZ/ EAWAG/ UBA/ UGOT/ UKCEH at the WP6 kick off meeting in Bilthoven. Additionally, the regulatory purpose of the project was discussed on a joint session on mixture regulation by UBA/UFZ (regulators/scientists) at the annual meeting of Topic 9 - One Health of the Helmholtz Program Earth and Environment at UFZ. (AGES, EAWAG, UBA, UFZ, REGIONH, BPI, UI, ISS, LSMU, STAMI, NIVA, IEP-NRI, ENSP, UAVR, KEMI, UGOT, NILZOH, EA, BUL, UKCEH).

➤ A6.4.2. Facilitate the regulatory acceptance and practical use of new methods

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS** has conducted several scoping activities in the period June-September 2022, in coordination with WP2 and WP3, as part of its mapping of the status of integration and use of NAMs across the various EU chemical sectors and risk assessment processes. A pilot exercise was conducted combining peer-review & gray literature review with expert consultation to better understand regulatory gaps and needs, and to inform the planning, development, and implementation of a broad expert consultation exercise. In September 2022 we conducted structured interviews with EU risk assessment and chemical safety experts (regulatory and industry) at EU level (Commission and Member States), the UK and Switzerland. This expert elicitation phase informs the development of an online survey to target European chemical risk assessors during the period October-December 2022.
- **P6.4.2.b_Y1_NGRA_applied_in_practice_NIPH_VKM** started in May 2022 with a planning and scoping phase combining literature review and expert consultation to identify existing tools for evaluating in vitro and in silico studies in a hazard/risk assessment context. To avoid duplicating efforts and create synergies with major US and EU science and regulatory organisations with similar aims and objectives, as well as to recruit specific subject matter expertise in risk assessment and evidence synthesis methods use & tool development, VKM has successfully established an external scientific Advisory Group including 13 participants (Anna Beronius (Karolinska Institutet), Fleur van Broekhuizen (ECHA), Patience Browne (OECD), Ingrid Druwe (U.S. EPA), Thomas Hartung (CAAT, Johns Hopkins), Sebastian Hoffmann (EBTC), Carlijn Hooijmans (Radboud University), George Kass (EFSA), Pilar Prieto-Peraita (JRC), Joshua Robinson (University of California San Francisco), Erwin Roggen (ONTOX), Andrew Rooney (NIEHS), Mathieu Vinken (ONTOX, ASPIS) as well as WP2 and WP3 representatives as observers). Preparatory work for setting the Advisory Group was done in August and September 2022, in close collaboration with WP3, with inputs from WP2 and ANSES. These activities involved drafting a Terms of Reference. The first Advisory group meetings were held in September 2022, which started the work on developing the protocols for evaluation of internal and external validity of in vitro studies. **P6.4.2.c_Y1_ML-AI-QSAR_UT** started with an exploratory analysis (scoping exercise) for defining the research priorities, incl. target chemical groups and properties, through literature review and consultation with partners (May-August 2022). Due to shared interest with P6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS, the project is conducted jointly with UNIBAS. Specific inputs were therefore given to UNIBAS to review the literature to support the development of working definitions for artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) methods; and develop questions specific to in silico methods to be included in the online survey (August-September 2022). The outcome of the literature review will serve to collect AI&ML-driven QSARs published in the scientific journals and public resources (e.g. source code repositories) (October-December 2022).

- A6.4.3. Developing information transfer structures and enforcement methodology for chemicals in articles to support the transition to a circular economy

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- **P 6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU** will evaluate the currently available information on substances in products and materials and how this information can be integrated in enforcement activities and life cycle assessments, based on a comprehensive review of chemical databases and gap and needs analysis of analytical testing methodologies. In P 6.4.3.a_Y1_SuProM_MU, the initial landscaping exercises were initiated in three key aspects:
 - 1. Development of a survey distributed to national chemical agencies to gather information on the current use of databases for the implementation and enforcement of chemical regulations, as well as what enforcement activities are done at a regional/national level. This survey was distributed with the support of WP3. This identified agencies that will be active stakeholders in the continuation of P 6.4.3.a.
 - 2. Mapping of existing (outside of PARC) activities on substances in products and materials, to evaluate the methods used to gather information on substances in products and materials. This was summarised in an internal online workshop in December 2022.
 - 3. Inventorying of existing databases that can be used to inform on substances in products and materials in conjunction with basic information regarding scope, access, and methods. This was informed from the survey outcomes as well as the internal expertise of the project team.
- A6.4.4. Risk assessment to support and promote efficient overall protection of biodiversity

Project progress (as described in the AWP Y1 SRIA):

- In **P6.4.4.a_Y1_CS1_KEMI** a series of meetings and workshops have been organised (KEMI, UBA, FOEN). Details on these meetings and workshops including a summary of the minutes will be indicated in the deliverable AD 6.7 (Technical report outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas, M24)
- The purpose has been to map regulatory needs as expressed in EU Green Deal strategies (e.g. Chemicals strategy / PARC concept paper, Farm to fork and Biodiversity strategy) as well as individual bodies strategies (e.g. EFSA PERA initiative) and transform them into ERA development needs and subsequently into research questions, into identified data gaps and into project deliverables. The meetings and workshops have involved the regulatory core group (KEMI, UBA, FOEN, EFSA and ANSES), project leaders (CKB, UFZ, UKOLD and ISCIII) as well as other partners. An online kick-off meeting involving all partners in 6.4.4 took place on 16 June. A two-half-days physical kick-off workshop involving also all partners in 6.4.4 was held October 6-7 in Berlin. Meetings have also been organised to establish connections to new partners with strategic competence and data resources in ERA and landscape ecology. Work remains to identify and fully integrate available resources among the partners involved in 6.4.4 in terms of data, tools and research competence.
- **P6.4.4.b_Y1_CS2_SLU** aims at exploring ways of simplifying the Predicted Environmental Concentration (PEC) calculations within the Ecological Risk Assessment (ERA). Monitoring datasets and predictive model tools have been identified. Collaboration with WP 4.2 on

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gathering monitoring datasets throughout the EU on national and regional level has been initiated. Recruitment of scientific staff has also been done.

- **P6.4.4.c_Y1_CS3_UFZ** aim to develop a protective ERA with reduced complexity and resources required while keeping it as information-rich as necessary. This will be achieved by including only the information and processes that have been proven by ecosystem monitoring and effect modelling to be relevant. Currently, the project is scoping a meta-database which will be used to gather information and data on monitoring of environmental effects that are species related (e.g. ecological and trait based), site related and methods related (e.g. omics data, trait and sensitivity based effect monitoring).
- **P6.4.4.d_Y1_CS4_UKOLD** aims to ensure that results of any independently performed ERA of a Plant Protection Products (PPP) can be used as a benchmark for ERAs of other PPPs, i.e. comparing and ranking risk profiles of PPPs among substances and in different areas (e.g. for selected organism groups) of the ERA when assessed on the basis of similar level of refinement. This project is still in the scoping and planning phase and the conceptual work has so far been conducted mainly in connection with P6.4.4.a_Y1_CS1_KEMI. Furthermore, data acquisition has begun.
- **P6.4.4.e_Y1_CS5_ISCIII** will develop and explore how landscape-based ERA integrating landscape structures and aggregated (several crops) and combined (several pesticides) exposures can be used to improve the current risk assessment methods. This project is in the conceptualisation phase. The project has started the identification of relevant areas for conducting the case studies and the networking with farmer associations, Integrated Pest Management (IPM) specialists and voluntary initiatives stakeholders to setup the design of each case studies. In parallel, the development of a conceptual model for the use of scenarios in landscape risk assessment has been initiated with a set of brainstorming workshops conducted during 2022.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

Not applicable

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

In general, the activities in the task are delayed by four-six months. The main reason is the short lead time between the approval of PARC application and formal project start, which has given limited time for partners to recruit research staff. There will therefore be a general need to transfer person months from year 1 to year 2 for most projects under 6.4.

The project 6.4.2.a_Y1_LandscapingSurvey_UNIBAS has experienced some delays due to intense and sustained administrative and coordination activities with internal PARC partners and external stakeholders, which have significantly slowed down the implementation of planned research activities during the period M1-M6. Several other factors have also contributed to the delays: (i) A number of research projects at EU (and international) level are currently up and running, with very similar aims and objectives to A6.4.2 (how to promote regulatory acceptance of NAMs). This required establishing a fruitful dialogue with a number of organisations outside PARC, as well as with partners across WPs and Tasks, to avoid duplication of efforts and create synergies inside and outside PARC; (ii) because

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the Swiss budget was only secured very late, the recruitment process for a new collaborator started late (and is still ongoing). Therefore, AD6.8 “Technical report: mapping exercise assessing the status of integration and use of NAMs across sectorial frameworks” has been postponed to M24, and will be merged with another Additional Deliverable AD.16. This will achieve better coherence, since both deliverables are overlapping, and form two parts of the landscaping exercise. We will report on the outcome of the expert consultation exercise (structured expert interviews, online survey) at the end of Y1.

The project P6.4.4.a_Y1_CS1_KEMI has been delayed in terms of contacts and engagement with regulators and policy makers. To avoid duplicate work and promote an efficient use of the time of regulatory agencies and other stakeholders, the dialogue needs to be coordinated with other parts of PARC via WP2 and WP3. Therefore, the Additional deliverable AD6.7 Technical reports outlining the regulatory needs for ERA development areas (M12) has been postponed to month 24. In Y1 this deliverable will be replaced by Draft reports outlining current state of consensus of regulatory needs for ERA development areas.

1.7. Work package 7. FAIR Data

1.7.1. Task 7.1. FAIR Data Policy and implementation²

Leader: TNO (NL), UOB (UK)

Participants: ANSES (FR), BRGM (FR), VITO (BE), MU(CZ), UZIS (CZ), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), KWR (NL), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), NIVA (N), UG-PL (PL), JSI (SI), KI (SE), AUTH (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing the first version of the PARC FAIR Data Policy (PFDP) and Data Management Plan (DMP), with PARC scientists, stakeholders and the FAIR community, and starting with the implementation of FAIR awareness and skills within PARC

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

General:

- Go FAIR Foundation subcontracted to deliver an integrated approach to training in FAIRification according to the three-point FAIRification framework (3PFF) and support in its concrete implementation, and to support the WP in development of conceptual models, vocabularies and ontologies. GFF provides expertise in all relevant FAIR principles, techniques, and technologies, such as persistent unique identifiers, controlled vocabularies, semantic modeling, and ontologies in order to be able to develop FAIR implementation profiles providing machine actionable metadata.
- WP7 online kick-off session on May 2022; 2-days physical and online meeting in Brno October 2022, plus numerous task-level and WP-level meetings.

Much of the work in WP7 in year 1 was transversal in nature, and significant effort was dedicated to understanding the needs of the other WPs and the first round of projects. Based on these ongoing discussions, WP7-specific projects will be defined during AWPY2 and beyond.

² The titles of the activities A7.1.1, A7.1.2 and A7.1.3 were not included in the AWPY1 and SRIA. These titles have been added between the submission of the AWP Y1 and the submission of the ASR Y1 and will be added in AWPY2 and its Annex PARC Portfolio project.

➤ A7.1.1 PARC Data Policy and Data Management Plan

The following activities were undertaken as part of the development of the initial PARC DMP:

- Collection and evaluation of a range of existing DMPs to identify the general and domain-specific best practice.
- Outlining of the content of the DMP, and assignment of drafting responsibilities for specific sections.
- Facilitation of several discussion and drafting sessions to add content to the initial PARC DMP, identify areas for additional clarification, and build consensus.
- Presentation of the initial DMP outline and proposed sign-off process to the PARC MB.
- Facilitation of feedback session from WPs / MB on the Initial DMP to ensure it captures all relevant concerns.
- Finalisation of the Initial DMP for submission.

In parallel, and intensively during the 2-day WP7 meeting in Brno, discussions got underway regarding the content of the PARC Data Policy – an initial Table of Contents (ToC) was prepared and authoring / text drafting responsibilities were assigned, with first drafts of the sections completed by end November 2022, with a further meeting held in early December 2022 to maintain momentum. The ToC was shared with the PARC MB on 10th October, with a request for feedback and any additional suggestions for topics to be covered by the November 7th MB meeting, as the PARC data policy will apply to all PARC partners and thus all should have an opportunity to feed into it.

No project submitted at present

➤ A7.1.2 Training and organisation

Role descriptions for the Data Champions and Data Liaisons, and the FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) were developed, and refined based on discussions within WP7 and with the broader PARC team. Once the roles were defined, the process of collecting volunteers for these roles was implemented, with all PARC projects expected to have a data Champion and a Data Liaison, but that each champion and liaison could be responsible for several projects whose activities are clustered based on the type of data they are working with, or the type of challenges they are facing in terms of their data management needs.

Training is a core component of the Task 7.1 activities, and has been aligned to the different roles and responsibilities identified as part of the DMP – namely Data Liaisons (from within WP7), data champions (from other WPs / Tasks / projects) and the FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) who are being trained as trainers to enable them to facilitate further training activities within PARC. The GO FAIR Foundation (GFF) have developed various training activities from FAIR awareness (bottom of the training pyramid as shown in Figure 7.1) up to the Metadata for Machines workshop (M4M) facilitators and trainers. The training to be provided to each of the data champions, data liaisons and FIT experts is shown schematically in Figure 7.1 below.

Figure 7.1. The GFF Training pyramid, with the basic level of training in FAIR Awareness and FAIR implementation Plans (FIPs) being given to all PARC members who are interested, to all WP7 members and to the Data Champions from across PARC. The Data Liaisons (who are embedded in WP7) will also receive training to enable them to facilitate FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) training and be introduced to the Metadata for Machines (M4M) concepts. The FIT experts will be able to further specialise their skills depending on their individual interests and PARC needs with vocabulary, data schema, FAIR datapoint (FDP), or Interoperable Descriptions of Observable Property (I-ADOPT) training, as shown in the training pyramid.

The timetable for training has been implemented and commenced in November and December 2022, as data champions and data liaisons were appointed to projects, and will continue throughout 2023 working on FIPs for the specific domains and use cases etc. The first Fair Awareness training was provided to WP7 and already available Data Champions on 6th October as part of the WP7 meeting in Brno, and a recording is available for use by Data Champions and Data Liaisons.

➤ A7.1.3 FAIR Data Use Case Coordination

Collaborative workflows have been designed and communicated, both for the onboarding of new PARC projects into the FAIR processes and for the triage and identification of FAIR Data Use Cases. At the same time, WP7 has agreed on a consolidated approach for following up the FAIRness of active projects and the status of the use case implementations.

For each of the projects, mixed data teams have been assigned (data champions and data liaisons, supported and trained by the GFF) that will provide bottom-up input and user validation to the selected use cases. For top-down domain input, subject matter expertise and FAIR data advice, overarching expert teams have been established (the cross-WP Ontology workgroup and the FAIR implementation Taskgroup).

FAIR Implementation Taskgroup (FIT) was established to receive further training from GFF and become FAIR data trainers capable of supporting the implementation of project-specific DMPs through provision of ongoing training and support.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
MS11	Network of trained FAIR data stewards	TNO/UOB	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

The summer period coming so soon after the kick-off meeting resulted in some delays to getting planning and coordination underway, especially of activities that involve cross-WP engagement such as the implementation of the Data Champions, however this is now well underway and progress will accelerate rapidly over the coming months.

1.7.2. Task 7.2. Data libraries

Leader: MU (CZ), VITO (BE)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AUTH (EL), BRGM (FR), EFSA (EU), EV-ILVO (BE), IISPV (ES), ISS (IT), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UFZ (DE), UG-PL (PL), UBA (DE), UL-LACDR (NL), UNILU (LU), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UU-IRAS (NL), UZIS (CZ), KWR (NL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Drafting overall landscape and FAIRness assessment of major databases, repositories, platforms relevant for PARC, and starting the development of solutions in first use cases

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A7.2.1 – Mapping the PARC Data Landscape³

Inventory of major databases, repositories and other relevant sources for chemical risk assessment has been initiated. Review of relevant sources based on common knowledge of individual partners, consultations with domain experts and further extensive research is ongoing. Furthermore, each of project partners was engaged to provide relevant sources from his/her country and field of expertise.

Inventory is focused on: transnational repositories with cross cutting content; domain specific repositories; national level resources and repositories. Inventory of relevant sources was further driven by WP7 project Chemicals in the environment which helped to elaborate to higher detail resources relevant to chemical exposure. Collaboration with WPs 4, 6, 8 and 9 was established to synchronise

³ The titles of the activities A7.2.1, A7.2.2 and A7.2.3 have been revised compared to the AWPY1. These titles have been changed between the submission of the AWP Y1 and the submission of the ASR Y1 and will be used as such in AWPY2 and its Annex PARC Portfolio project.

Previous A.7.2.1 title: Inventory major transnational and national databases, repositories or platforms for chemicals RA

approaches, metadata of repositories and to prioritise chemical compounds according to their current focus.

The inventory is being compiled for major resources but remain open for further additions and extensions. Discussions with DG ENV and JRC (e.g., workshop 25-26/10 2022) were initiated to align roadmaps for design and implementation. Discussions with IPCHEM staff have led to a draft agreement on collaboration on data sharing.

➤ A7.2.2 – PARC FAIR data hub⁴

FAIR implementation profile (FIP) efforts are being initiated, shared visions on required services and components are taking shape, and data sources to be interfaced within the first iteration are being identified.

From currently evolving requirements it is clear that the PARC FAIR Data Hub will need a data catalogue module. The Data Catalog should host metadata for data generated in PARC as well as those hosted elsewhere to fulfill the FAIR principles and requirements. A review of both commercial and open-source software tools is being conducted and the outcomes assessed in several rounds of internal discussions. The software review will be provided as a report that can be published.

WP7 has also initiated a consultation with WP2 on potential information exchange with PARCopedia and various WP8 projects on data exchange needs and use case identification.

The first year's use cases will help to identify core data hub services and the gaps to be filled in the future. A list of use cases will be developed to be considered when designing the first draft architecture. From these use cases the data hub related requirements will be extracted and prioritised.

➤ A7.2.3 Solutions for FAIR data: development and implementation⁵

The following data use cases were initiated:

- human biomonitoring datasets with T4.1, T6.2 and 8.3 (VITO),
- monitoring PFAS and endocrine disruptors with T4.2 (MU),

A workplan on FAIRification actions according to the 3PFF was drafted with GFF. From the various projects, fast movers have been identified, where data champions and data liaisons volunteered, and these projects are invited to share their requirements and participate in the Use Case identification process. For the other active projects, data champions and liaisons were assigned, and efforts are made to clarify the FAIR data goals and needs for data interaction in the project. This information is also used for Use Case identification by the FAIR Implementation Task group (FIT). All data liaisons were invited to participate in the ongoing FAIRification activities and trainings.

➤ A7.2.4 Standards and harmonisation⁶

⁴ Previous A.7.2.2 title: Implement a PARC FAIR data hub

⁵ Previous A.7.2.3 title: Concrete solutions will further be elaborated and implemented based on specific use cases

⁶ The number and title of activity A7.2.4 was not included in the AWPY1 and SRIA. This title has been added

WP7 established cooperation with GFF on the development of controlled vocabularies, semantic modeling, and ontologies.

A cross-work package working group on vocabularies & ontologies was established to further elaborate on – among other things - common PARC data model and vocabulary.

Project progress (addition from AWP Y1 SRIA): Those projects refer to all activities under T7.2

- **P7.2.2.a_Y1_chemicals-in-environment_MU_VITO:** The project started with mapping the existing data resources for exposure to chemicals in the environment. In collaboration with T4.2 priority was given to PFAS and endocrine disruptors. The Focus was on ambient air and water monitoring networks. For these matrices was developed a common template to capture core metadata which was further discussed and harmonised with WP4 and WP9.
- **P7.2.2.b_Y1_HBMdatasets_VITO:** The HBM4EU central data platform for individual HBM data is continued as the Personal Exposure and Health platform. A GDPR compliant Protocol has been elaborated and signed to allow reuse of the data from the HBM4EU Aligned studies and Mercury studies in PARC. It allows for accession of PARC partners who were not involved in HBM4EU. Discussion with IPCHEM has been initiated on their role in hosting HBM data in PARC. A planning has been made up for further FAIRification of HBM datasets in collaboration with GFF.

A first end-to-end data exchange has been set up between HBM data providers and a CRA modelling platform in the context of A6.2.3 (real life mixtures) and T8.3 (integrative models). Work started on a consistent vocabulary and identification for biomarkers. A first version of a quality control module that can be run locally, complying to GDPR, was delivered to the countries participating in the real-life mixtures study. A roadmap has been drafted to evolve this from a bilateral custom data exchange to a semantic interface that other data providers and consumers can use.

The experience is used as inspiration for creating an implementation template to be used in other FAIRification efforts. The T7.2 "FAIR and sustainable storage of human biomonitoring (HBM) datasets" use case, in collaboration with the T6.2 and T8.3 projects have adopted a pilot role in their work on A FAIR approach to human biomonitoring data exchanges. This experience will be used as a roadmap template for other use cases on FAIR collaboration.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023 for the task 7.2:

Not applicable

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, for the task 7.2 if any:

As noted for Task 7.1, the summer period resulted in some delays in activities getting off the ground, but work is now well underway and progress will accelerate rapidly over the coming months.

between the submission of the AWP Y1 and the submission of the ASR Y1 and will be added in AWPY2 and its Annex PARC Portfolio project.

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1.7.3. Task 7.3. Innovative analyses

Leader: UU-IRAS (NL), IISPV (ES)

Participants: ANSES (FR), AUTH, EV-ILVO (BE), IMROH (CR), INRS (FR), INSERM (FR), ISSeP (BE), JSI (SI), KI (SE), KWR (NL), MU (CZ), NIVA (NO), UL-LACDR (NL), UNIVIE (AT), UOB (UK), UU (SE), UZIS (CZ), VITO (BE), WR (NL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Performing scoping studies to investigate and select innovative approaches to optimise use and insights from FAIR data, and to assess uncertainty; identifying use cases for implementation and evaluation of selected approaches

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A7.3.1 Innovative methods for combined analyses of FAIR (heterogeneous) data

The planned scoping review has been started and a list of inventories of different statistical approaches and computational tools suitable for / used in meta- and pooled analysis has been made, and a workflow for meta-analysis task has been proposed (see Figure 7.2). In parallel, possible use cases with available exposure, toxicological or epidemiological heterogeneous data were discussed. These use cases will be elaborated in detail in the scoping review and used to demonstrate the different approaches discussed.

No project submitted at present.

Figure 7.2: A proposed workflow for meta-analysis

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 for the activity 7.3.1, if any:

Slightly delayed start because of leadership problem, whereby the previous co-Task leader and leader of this activity UU-IRAS (NL) has left WP7 due to budgetary constraints. Discussions have been held with possible alternate activity co-leads and will be updated once they have formally confirmed who will be lead and co-lead (VITO/AUTH). For the scoping study, no problem was encountered during the implementation of the work planned during this period. However, we may experience common challenges of aligning partners' expectations in 2-3 use cases, and also finding a common use case data set to work in year 2 and following years. The Task/activity co-leads will monitor this.

➤ A7.3.2 Methods for uncertainty characterisation, propagation and quantification as a basis for harmonisation in RA

A planned scoping review has been started. Different groups related to prioritised outcomes were constituted: a core group (CG) with expertise in methods for uncertainty analysis; six specialty groups for exposure, hazard, risk and health impact assessment, and IATAs. The groups started working by scoping studies and a draft has been prepared by IISPV and circulated to members for their further contribution. This collaborative work will result in a manuscript and a final draft will be ready by March 2023. Selection of use cases has started for each specialty group and will be finalised by Dec 2022.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 for the activity 7.3.2:

For the scoping study, there is no problem encountered during the implementation of the work planned during this period. However, we may experience common challenges of aligning partners' expectations in domain-specific case studies from exposure, hazard, risk and health impact assessment, and IATAs, and in collaboration with WP4,5,6. The discussion has already started but finding a common use case data /problem is still ongoing. We expect it may get more clarified as once other WPs get more organised with their tasks.

➤ A7.3.3. Novel computational methods for integrating and extracting knowledge from non-structured data

The activity 7.3.3 team has prepared a detailed project covering the two activities planned for this task and a revised version of P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV with a detailed task description will be included in the Annex of the AWPY2.

Project progress (addition to the AWP Y1 SRIA)

- **P7.3.3.a_Y1_ALT-IST_IISPV** A scoping study and an inventory of ontology-based approaches and frameworks for knowledge integration is being developed. A detailed discussion on use cases, specifically in close relation to the use case on “databases of chemicals in articles with A6.4.3” and AOPs developments in T5.3 has been started. A detail plan for each use cases is being prepared to further refine and prioritise the particular endpoints or chemical classes/imported products in collaboration with WP5 and WP6. An excel inventory of the various tools and approaches that the partners have available has been compiled as the basis for matching of tools to the regulatory questions and selection of demonstrators.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 for the activity 7.3.3:

Slightly delayed start. After the dropping out of UU-IRAS, the current co-lead IISPV was leading this activity solo, but now a new co-lead, UoB has been selected and agreed to work on this task.

For the scoping study, there is no problem encountered during the implementation of the work planned during this period. However, we may experience common challenges of aligning partners' expectations in domain-specific case studies as there is still no defined scope in other WPs. We expect it may get more clarified as once other WPs get more organised with their tasks.

- A7.3.4 – Identify additional needs in PARC for innovative analyses and promising evolutions in the data science landscape, and translate them in use cases for evaluation

The objective of this activity is to identify emerging needs in PARC for innovative analyses on one hand, and promising innovative techniques on the other hand. For this year, we have taken two case studies for the scoping study, which will be further refined and implemented in subsequent years.

Activity 7.3.4 has taken a new use case in consultation with WP5 and WP8 and has started working on Activity 7.3.4.a. Pharmacophore modelling using machine learning for screening BBB permeation of xenobiotics. This activity is complementing with data generated in Task 5.1a and the computational tools for the early warning system in Task 8.2.

Activity 7.3.4 is collaborating with A6.4.3: AI&ML-driven computational NAMs for use in NGRA lead by UT (EE) and work on Landscaping and readiness of NAMs based on advanced AI&ML approaches for use in chemical RA

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 for the activity 7.3.4:

No problem encountered.

List of the deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023 for the task 7.3:

Not applicable

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022 for the task 7.3:

Described under each activity of the task 7.3

1.8. Work package 8. Concepts and Toolboxes

1.8.1. Task 8.1. Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD)

Leader: RIVM (NL), EMPA (CH), AUTH (EL)

Participants: INERIS (FR), BNN (AT), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UNINA (IT), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), FMUL (PT), NIC (SI), INSST (ES), IVL (SE), BUL (UK), Cefas-Defra (UK)

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Specific objective of the task for Y1: Increasing the knowledge on methods related to SSbD and providing an inventory of the methods and tools to put SSbD into practice, paving the way towards the operationalisation of the SSbD framework developed by the EC across the various users (industry, regulatory bodies and in academia)

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

Focus has been paid to the development of an efficient communication plan and infrastructure blueprint for an effective science-policy-user interphase, resulting in inclusive dialogue with the EC, users and relevant stakeholders inside and outside PARC, resulting in a collection of first indication on the gaps, barriers, and incentives to gain insight in the completeness, feasibility and applicability of the EC JRC framework has been carried out.

For the development of the toolbox, an inventory and review of existing tools that are currently available from existing initiatives on SbD (nano) and SSbD has been carried out. Based on this review, and accounting for the steps identified in the JRC methodology for SSbD assessment, user requirements and functional specifications of the PARC SSbD toolbox are mapped out. In addition, the requirements for use of FAIR data are also explored. In practice, the toolbox is designed to accommodate the translation of the criteria for SSbD and to collate the necessary knowledge along the entire value chain. In this context, an inventory of existing toolboxes and assessment of their applicability will be made to assist in the operationalisation of the SSbD concept in chemical management and innovation. Identification of the most optimal set of parameters for selecting potential use cases to test the methodology developed by the EC and complement the use cases chosen by the EC has also been carried out and based on the discussions so far in Activity 8.1.1 and 8.1.2, a set of potential case studies has been formulated that will allow the testing of the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, engaging relevant stakeholders in the value chain, accounting for on the barriers as well as incentives for implementation of different stakeholders that are involved in the use cases. Cooperation with IRISS on value chain interaction is initiated. The development of a systematic approach for knowledge sharing as well as education within PARC and with relevant stakeholders outside PARC (“inception plan”), included the development of an inventory of platforms, initiatives and materials for knowledge and information sharing.

➤ A8.1.1. Translate EC SSbD criteria & methodology towards operationalisation

No project submitted at present.

In Activity 8.1.1, particular focus has been paid to the development of an efficient communication plan and infrastructure blueprint for an effective science-policy-user interface, resulting in an inclusive dialogue process with the EC, users and relevant stakeholders inside and outside PARC. EU project IRISS is an important partner in addressing the specific needs of the value chains. On top of that, and to keep pace with the state of the art and the lessons learned, a collection of first indications regarding gaps, barriers, and incentives to gain insight in the completeness, feasibility and applicability of the EC JRC framework has been carried out. This was also highlighted in the respective technical kick-off meeting of the activity that took place on 20/09/2022 where the links with the policy developments through contributions from DG RTD, JRC and ECHA were made explicit. To facilitate the process, a communication plan has been coined with the aim to cover:

- (a) a structured dialogue with the EC; (AUTH, RIVM, DTU)
- (b) communication inside the PARC consortium (AUTH, RIVM, IVL, DTU, NILU, SYKE, ISS) and outside the PARC consortium (RIVM, AUTH, BNN, IVL, DTU, NILU, INERIS, SYKE, UBA, EMPA, INSST).

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The communication plan will be implemented in close collaboration with WP3.

In order to review the gaps, incentives and barriers for the practical application of EC framework for SSbD criteria and methodology, the following actions are currently ongoing:

- Gathering of lessons learned from best practices focusing on the ‘by-design’ (RIVM, AUTH, INSST, ISS, INERIS, TTL, NILU, IUSS, DTU, UBA);
- Identification of gaps, barriers, and assessment of completeness, feasibility and applicability of the framework for SSbD criteria by means of focus groups through interviews with all relevant stakeholder groups; in addition, stakeholders will be provided a questionnaire to address these issues comprehensively (IUSS, INSST, TTL, SYKE, RIVM, BNN).
- Keeping pace with state of the art (RIVM, TTL, NILU, UBA, AUTH, INERIS). Towards this aim, the SSbD expertise developed within the EU projects RiskGONE and SABYDOMA, and CEFIC-LRI project DOREMI will facilitate the contacts with these projects and the participation to the EC SSbD network. Additionally, a review on risk assessment and management SbD SOPs applicable in early development of nanomaterials is currently ongoing, while this experience will be further explored for broader applications on other chemicals and materials.

➤ A8.1.2. Toolbox development

Projects progress (as described in the AWP1 SRIA):

• **P8.1.2.a_Y1_SSbDToolbox_AUTH**

For the development of the toolbox, an inventory and review of existing tools that are currently available from existing initiatives on SbD (nano) and SSbD has been carried out. Based on this review, and accounting for the steps identified in the JRC methodology for SSbD assessment, user requirements and functional specifications of the PARC SSbD toolbox are mapped. A list of actions is currently being implemented to aid in this process:

- Determination of Gaps and Opportunities (RIVM, UBA, IVL, BUL, UNINA, NILU, TTL)
- Priorities for Innovation; Identification of information needs along the innovation process (EMPA, RIVM, ISS, BUL, NILU, UNINA, TTL)

In addition, the modalities and need for use of FAIR data is also explored. In practice, the toolbox is designed to accommodate the implementation of the SSbD framework and test its applicability with a view to optimising its practical exploitation.

The translation of the framework for Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) chemicals and materials is essential to collate the necessary along the entire value chain. In this context, an inventory of tools in existing toolboxes and assessment of their applicability is being made to assist in the operationalisation of the SSbD concept in chemical management and innovation. In order to operationalise the SSbD framework, existing tools (IVL, IUSS, AUTH, EMPA, NILU, IVL, TTL, RIVM), as well as tools developed within PARC (AUTH, IUSS, RIVM, NILU, IVL, ISS), are being identified and adapted. Furthermore, the conceptual design of the toolbox is being carried out (AUTH, EMPA, IUSS, NILU, BUL, IVL, ISS). Based on this conceptual design, the implementation of the compiled tools into the alpha version of toolbox is currently ongoing (AUTH, IUSS, EMPA, NILU). Towards this aim, existing knowledge gained on toolbox development in other EU SbD and SSbD initiatives is brought in and a direct link with the IRISS project has been established (RIVM, EMPA) to explore the user needs for the toolbox functionalities. The review of existing tools for SSbD assessment has contributed to the determination of gaps and opportunities of the SSbD toolbox regarding data and tool requirements (AUTH). Key input incorporated in the toolbox is also the knowledge and experience on tools for risk and sustainability assessment, as well as the experience of other modelling tools for RA that account for

chemical risk and sustainability assessment such as the INTEGRA LCA (AUTH). At the same time, close collaboration with Task 8.3 has been established, to ensure the proper linkage of the PARC SSbD toolbox within the overall PARC model network (AUTH).

➤ A8.1.3. Towards operationalisation: Use case & indicators

In Activity 8.1.3, most of the work carried out so far regards the definition of suitable criteria to select potential use cases to test the methodology developed by the EC and complement the use cases chosen by the EC. Based on the discussions so far in Activity 8.1.1 and 8.1.2 and according to such criteria, a set of potential case studies has been formulated. The following actions are currently underway to facilitate the definition and execution of use cases:

- Pilot case study/studies for better common understanding of the SSbD components (IVL)
- Establishment of case studies criteria (IVL, UNINA, EMPA, NILU, RIVM)
- Finding suitable case studies and organising case studies (IVL)
- Operation of case studies; first iteration (IVL)
- Summary of learnings and feedback to EC (IVL)
- Determination of Gaps and Opportunities (RIVM, UBA, IVL, BUL, UNINA, NILU, TTL)

The use cases are defined with a view to allow the testing of the applicability of the EC SSbD criteria and methodology, engage relevant stakeholders along the value chain, consider barriers as well as incentives for implementation relevant to the stakeholders that are involved in the use cases (AUTH). Moreover, an initial inventory of relevant indicators to follow the progresses of sector applicability of the toolbox is made, accounting for initiatives by the EC, including the indicator programme foreseen by EEA and in collaboration with task 3.2 (NILU). Experience on case studies formulation has been brought by several partners work in the domain of nanomaterials and nano-enabled products (RIVM, EMPA).

➤ A8.1.4 Knowledge sharing & Education as key factors for efficient SSbD operationalisation

Work carried out in Activity 8.1.4 has been focused on the development of a systematic approach for knowledge sharing as well as education and training within PARC and with relevant stakeholders outside PARC (“inception plan”). This included the development of an inventory on platforms, initiatives and materials for knowledge and information sharing, and education related to SSbD (RIVM, AUTH, UNINA, DTU, IUSS, TTL), the identification of relevant stakeholders and strategies of how to reach them and finally (UBA, RIVM, AUTH, UNINA, IUSS), the connection to WP2 and more specifically to PARCopedia (AUTH) and WP9 and in particular to Task 9.4 training (RIVM, AUTH, UBA, IVL) to develop an approach of how knowledge and education on SSbD can be facilitated within PARC.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D8.1	Report on the conceptual design of the SSbD toolbox	AUTH/EMPA/RIVM	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.8.2. Task 8.2. Scientific and technical basis for an Early warning system (EWS) on chemical risks

Leader: SLU (SE), INSERM (FR)

Participants: INRAE (FR), AU (DK), UBA (DE), ISS (IT), IRFM (IT), UniLU (LU), UU-IRAS (NL), VUA (NL), WR (NL), NILU (NO), NMBU (NO), UG-PL (PL), DGS (PT), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), ORU (SE), IVL (SE), SLV (SE), UMU (SE), EA (UK), AUTH (EL), EFET (EL), NKUA (EL), UOC (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Developing concepts and protocols for early warning monitoring tools, creating the prioritisation framework

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A8.2.1 EW monitoring tools

Projects progress (as described in the AWP1 SRIA):

- **P8.2.1.a_Y1_EWS_SLU**

Within T8.2.1, standardised protocols for early warning monitoring tools are currently under development (SLU, INRAE, UniLU, NILU, AU, MTM-ORU, NKUA, UU, VITO, EA), in collaboration with the work done in WP4, with a particular focus on suspect/non-targeted/EDA-based tools for both environmental (SLU, MTM-ORU) and human samples (INRAE, UOC, ISS, VITO). In line with the introduction of NAMs in the RA process, metabolomics-based biomarkers have been defined, together with computational tools that allow their proper interpretation, such as AI methods and advanced bioinformatics algorithms (WFSR, UMU, MTM-ORU, INSERM, UG, AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UU, IISPV). Towards the aim of information collation, monthly meetings have been organised (SLU). Close collaboration has also been ensured with a dedicated project under task 4.3 (SLU, AU, UU, VITO) to ensure good integration of EWS expectations with regard to innovative screening methods. Moreover, results of monitoring studies (in collaboration with other partners and WP 4) are currently analysed to prioritise substances which are “safe” or with adverse properties, also considering the JANUS software for prioritisation (IRFM). Scoping out metadata terms and suspect lists relevant for this task, along with prioritisation of use data, as well as keywords for scientific and grey literature search for EWS in food safety that are using AI and/or big data analytics (WFSR, UMU, MTM-ORU, INSERM, UG, AUTH, IRFM, NKUA, UU, IISPV) has also been carried out, to search public scientific databases and various EWS systems were identified (AUTH). Main features of the identified systems are now detailed and reported. Also, a literature analysis of existing AI systems in EWS and the summarizing overview in the context of their reliability and usefulness for chemicals prioritisation regarding toxicity is currently ongoing, while an extensive review of the operational EWS from England, namely Prioritisation and Early Warning System (PEWS) for chemicals of emerging concern, has also been completed (EA, AUTH).

➤ A8.2.2: Identification framework

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Towards the development of the identification framework in A8.2.2, databases with chemical structure and identifier information have been selected to facilitate the development of computational method for systematic identification and prioritisation of new substances (NKUA, UMU, AUTH). Human biomonitoring samples including available long-term target and non-target screening data from the German environmental specimen bank that are relevant for this task (UBA), and a curated list of currently marketed substances together with other relevant information is collated (UBA). Molecular features which are connected to adverse or critical effects (IRFM, AUTH), from a human toxicological point of view also considering environmental and ecotoxicological aspects are collected, initially characterised by structural alerts (thus local, molecular features) and global parameters (thus properties related to the whole molecule). Metadata terms and suspect lists relevant for this task have been scoping out, along with prioritisation of use data in cooperation with WP7 and WP4 (AU, INERIS, SLV, MTM, NMBU, SLU-IVM, SLU-BVF, NKUA, UBA, EA). Work on the evaluation of existing computational methods and selection of the most promising tools in the context of prioritisation framework is also carried out (UMU, INSERM, AUTH, IRFMN, UG, UniLU, UU), together with a review of scientific articles to recognise main principles and the mechanisms that the system relies on to determine and identify emerging risks (AUTH, SLU). Furthermore, a review of the European institutions libraries (i.e. ECHA, EFSA), grey literature in scientific and public databases (NGO) using keywords for EWS using machine learning to detect hazardous substances in the food safety area has been carried out (INSERM, AUTH). A key work relevant to the identification framework, is the review of the DG ENV Pilot project, that focused on emerging chemical risks to the environment, new substances at research and development stage, new synthetic substances on the market and known or unknown substances that have already been present for some time and for which emerging evidence raises concerns (AUTH).

➤ A8.2.3: Validation of EWS in case-studies

Review of existing studies for the identification of possible case studies that can be used for establishment of early warning monitoring tools and prioritisation framework for humans (SLU, AUTH, INRAE, IISPV, UOC, VITO), environment (SLU, MTM, SLV, UOC, EFET, UU), and products (SLU, INRAE, UU) is ongoing; at the moment, two relevant projects, have been identified, (a) one that makes use of long-term non-target screening data in the German riverine environment (UBA) and (b) one in an industrially contaminated area in Greece (AUTH).

➤ A8.2.4: Computational framework to support EWS

For the development of the computational framework to support the EWS, a review of existing initiatives has been carried out (AUTH, NKUA, UMU). Given the importance of access to data to feed the EWS, active collaboration with WP7, regarding the FAIR principles to make them accessible for researchers, regulators, policy and other stakeholders (e.g. NORMAN) has been ensured (NKUA, UMU, SLU, UniLU). The evaluation of the available in silico systems and chemical and toxicological screening data for the development of a systematic scoring system to rank and prioritise substances using multicriteria decision analysis is carried out (IRFMN, UG-PL), and the gaps identification will feed the design of the PARC EWS (AUTH). Additional work in A8.2.2 includes the incorporation of a computational framework for screening possible neurotoxins and the prediction of substance transfer across the BBB using AI/ML (IISPV), in line with experimental work and data generated in Task 5.1a. Finally, updates on the NORMAN Suspect List Exchange (NORMAN-SLE) relevant for this task before the end of the year are also introduced, providing feedback on the needs of EWS (NKUA, UMU, MTM, SLU).

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD8.1	Concept and plan of effect-based monitoring of chemicals in the environment	SLU/INSERM	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
D8.2	Report on the conceptual design and development guidelines of the PARC EWS	SLU/INSERM	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.8.3. Task 8.3. Integrative models

Leader: WR (NL), AUTH (EL)

Participants: ANSES (FR), INERIS (FR), ISSeP (BE), MU (CZ), DTU (DK), SYKE (FI), TTL (FI), IRFM (IT), IUSS (IT), UL-LACDR (NL), UU-IRAS (NL), WU-TOX (NL), NIVA (NO), NMBU (NO), NIC (SI), IISPV (ES), INSST (ES), UU (SE), UOC (EL)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Deriving the user requirements and the overarching conceptual model for the PARC integrative risk modelling network

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

➤ A8.3.1: Modelling network, model governance and user requirements

For developing a better understanding on the needs of the modelling network, stakeholders have been contacted through an online survey (AUTH, WR, IUSS) and in selected interviews to propose an overview of needs, regulatory user requirements and boundary conditions for relevant RA questions, in addition to the information they receive about existing or planned models (AUTH, WR) across PARC. Task Leaders of 8.3 (AUTH, WR) are also in close collaboration with WPs 3, 4, 5 and 6, receiving input for modelling needs of these WPs and to accommodate their needs in potential case studies. At the moment, the inventory of existing front-end access platforms has been completed (AUTH, WR, DTU, SYKE, IUSS) and a critical review from the user-perspective is carried out (IUSS, UOC). In addition, a case study on bisphenols has been selected as an initial set of use cases (AUTH, IUSS), that comprises a set of compounds both data rich (BPA) and data poor (BPS, BPF and other BPA alternatives).

➤ A8.3.2: Designing and implementing the PARC model network

Projects progress (as described in the AWPI SRIA):

- **P8.3.2.a_Y1_DIMN_AUTH**

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The key component of the work foreseen in Task 8.3 for Y1 was the first draft of an overarching conceptual model (AUTH, WR), to map models and platforms to user requirements (AUTH, WR, ANSES, INSERM, IRFM, IISPV) and RA questions (WR, ANSES, INSERM). In this direction, the conceptual PARC model has been designed (AUTH, WR) as an open-source dynamical system under version control, to allow continuous development and adaptation to regulatory needs to create web service connections between models and platforms in the area of chemical RA, covering the whole source to effect and impacts continuum. In the Task 8.3 kick-off meeting, held virtually on 26/09/2022, all partners had the opportunity to present models such as MCRA, INTEGRA, USEtox, VEGAHUB, ConsExpo, PACEM, (AUTH, WR, ANSES, INSERM, INERIS, ISSeP, DTU, SYKE, IRFM, IUSS, UL-LACDR, UU-IRAS, NIVA, IISPV, INSST, UU, UOC) which facilitated the process for the preparation to connect them in the PARC model network. Uncertainty issues across the overall chain of calculations have been discussed as well (MU, IISPV, WR, AUTH), in close collaboration with Task 7.3. Six focus groups have been proposed (integrated platforms and cross cutting issues (AUTH, WR, DTU, UU, IISPV, VITO), QSAR models (IRFM, UT), PBK models (INERIS, AUTH, IISPV, IUSS, ANSES, WR), hazard models (IRFM, UL-LACDR, AUTH, WR), and application in case studies (NIC, NIVA, NMBU, VITO, VUA, WU-TOX) to organise practical collaborations for the PARC model network. Task 8.3 is also member of the cross-WP group on development of a PARC ontology (WR, IISPV, AUTH, VITO), to support FAIR data sharing and model integration within the PARC model network. With regard to individual model development to be included in the model network:

- Initial links between the MCRA model (WR) and tools for HBM data (VITO) analysis were established, to support the research activities in the real-life mixtures project (6.2.3). In addition, multivariate statistical methods for real-life mixture selection from HBM data were implemented in MCRA, and functionality to link PBK models (INERIS) to MCRA was developed.
- The developers of INTEGRA (AUTH) are working on the link of internal dose estimates of parent compounds and metabolites with system biology models (UOC, IUSS), towards systems biology based AOPs (INSERM). In order to render INTEGRA interoperable with the rest of the model network, modifications will be done in the direction of following the common input-outputs formats (entry points) that will be commonly decided in T8.3 for the PARC model network, including necessary modules for adapting to the required spatial and temporal scale(s).
- The UNEP/SETAC global scientific consensus model USEtox (<https://usetox.org>) was adapted to include risk screening metrics applicable for use in European chemical RA (DTU), while being fully consistent with mass balance-based approaches used in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) assessment as e.g. implemented in the European Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) and SSbD frameworks, both coordinated by JRC. The adaptations under PARC ASRY1 cover both chemical emissions along product and technology life cycles as well as chemicals in product and process applications, and are internal contributions to PARC from the USEtox International Centre.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
AD8.2	First draft conceptual model describing models in the modular network and their connections	WR/AUTH	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

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D8.3	Report on the conceptual design of the integrative tools	WR/AUTH	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected
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Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

➤ A8.3.3 Application of the integrative model network in use cases

This activity has not started during the Y1 of PARC.

1.9. Work package 9. Building Infrastructural and human capacities

1.9.1. Task 9.1. Laboratory networking

Leader: ISCIII

Participants: ANSES, INERIS, Oniris, BRGM, LNE, ISSeP, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, IPA, RSU, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, FMUL, INSA, SZU-SK, UK, CSIC, FISABIO, FNS, BPI, GCSL

Specific objective of the task for Y1: i) Establishing the network of WP9 partners, contact points from other Work Packages (WPs), and expert groups, ii) identifying priority infrastructural needs through consultations with WPs 2-8, ii) finding consensus on the overall architecture of information catalogues, iii) landscaping and developing pilot information catalogues and networks for laboratories

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

The network of task 9.1 partners has been established. Consultations with other WPs on the laboratory networking needs and priority areas are performed on an ongoing basis supported by contact points, especially with WP4, on human biomonitoring and environmental monitoring.

The structure and characteristics of catalogues are being defined in collaboration with WP7 and several meetings were held for this purpose in Oct/Nov 2022, in the frame of Task 9.1 and 9.2.

The collection of information from laboratories in the field of human biomonitoring has been initiated in close collaboration and coordination with Task 4.1 (in particular activity 4.1.2), and the initial catalogue will be available by M12 (ISCIII has led the activity with the contribution from ANSES, LNE, ISSeP, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, IPA, NPHSL, LNS, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, FMUL, INSA, SZU-SK, UK, CSIC, FISABIO, FNS, BPI, GCSL).

Regarding the creation of air, indoor or consumer products laboratory catalogues, partners with expertise in these fields have been identified through consultation. ISCIII and MU led this activity, with contribution from Task 9.1 and 9.2 partners.

Survey formatting, distribution, and collection were discussed and aligned with WP2 and WP3 (Oct/Nov 2022). A self-administered online survey was developed to gather information on laboratory availability and capacities in the different fields. One specific survey for HBM was distributed in collaboration with activity 4.1.2 among PARC partners and beyond, to detect laboratories interested in being a member of the network. Another survey, including information about biomarkers and analytical capacities will be launched at the beginning of 2023. Regarding laboratories on air, indoor and articles (consumer products), planned by Y1, other surveys will be developed early in 2023, to detect laboratories with expertise in these fields and their capacities. Data collected in the surveys will be analysed/compiled in the specific catalogues.

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The collection of information from partners and laboratories depends on the availability and dissemination of surveys. The interdependency of activities in PARC in general and in this activity in particular with WP2 and WP3, to define the format and distribution in a coordinated way, might delay the information collection and thereby the initial catalogues.

T9.1 has been working mainly in A9.1.1 over these 8 months of PARC, to create the initial catalogues of laboratories. A9.1.2 and 9.1.3 as described in the AWPY1 SRIA will be in charge of develop networking activities to secure the coordination and activity of the networks and the development of the less developed networks. These will be done over the next years, once the networks and members had been identified. A9.1.4 will define the design of the laboratory dashboard, to be done in 2023.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D9.1	Initial laboratory catalogue and design of the network platform (dashboard) Y1	ISCIII	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.9.2. Task 9.2. Building exposure monitoring capacities

Leader: MU

Participants: ANSES, Inserm, Oniris, LNE, SpF, ISSeP, Sciensano, IMROH, AU, NPHC, NPHSL, LNS, UU-IRAS, STAMI, FMUL, INSA, ENSP, SZU-SK, CSIC, ISCIII, AUTH, BPI, GCSL

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Establishing the network of WP9 partners, contact points from other WPs, and expert groups, ii) identifying priority infrastructural needs through consultations with WPs 2-8, ii) finding consensus on the overall architecture of information catalogues, iii) landscaping and developing pilot information catalogues and networks for exposure monitoring networks.

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

Task 9.2 partners (MU) has led the activity with the contribution from ANSES, AU, AUTH, GCSL, INSERM, NPHHC, RIVM, SpF, and UU-IRAS) contributed to the mapping and discussion of the existing platforms and systems potentially suitable for building the catalogues of environmental and biomonitoring networks. Possible solutions were presented to partners in WP9 and WP7 (Oct-Nov 2022), due to the need to take into account FAIR aspects already in the initial phase of catalogue building, and summarised in a report (Oct/Nov 2022).

In addition, the development of catalogues on air monitoring (in cooperation with 4.2) and Human Biomonitoring/population studies/networks (in collaboration with 4.1) and on networks related to articles/indoors (in cooperation with 6.4.3), including the available sample and data collections in support of their further use in WPs 4-8, was initiated, where the initial inventories will be available by M12 (AU (domains: air, articles, indoor), CSIC (domain: air), ISCIII (domain: HBM), ISSeP (domains:

air, articles, indoor), FMUL (domain: HBM), NPHSL (domain: air), with contributions from BPI, GCSL, IMROH, INSA, JSI, LNE, LNS, ONIRIS, STAMI, SCIENSANO, SZU-SK, ENSP, UU-IRAS, VSCHT).

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D9.2	Catalogues on environmental and biomonitoring networks Y1	MU	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

1.9.3. Task 9.3. Joint activities – harmonisation

Leader: WR (NL)

Participants: ANSES, INRAE, INERIS, BRGM, LNE, UNIVIE, Sciensano, MU, VSCHT, AU, RegionH-RH, UCPH, UBA, IPA, LNS, WR, NIPH, STAMI, NMBU, UNN, INSA, JSI, NLZOH, CSIC, ISCIII, FNS, BPI, GCSL

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Harmonising Quality Assurance (QA)/Quality Control (QC) protocols/guidance for sampling, analysis and toxicity testing

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

A core working group with representatives from WP9 (WR), WP4 (ISCII, AU, ONIRIS) and WP5 (NIPH, STAMI) was established, first ideas on possible topics for generic QA/QC were exchanged, and a first alignment with more dedicated QA/QC within WP4 and WP5 tasks was done. This was presented and discussed among all WP9.3 contributors. Next, for each of the three activities defined in WP9.3 (sampling, generic QA/QC for chemical analysis, and generic QA/QC in toxicity testing and toxicokinetics) topics were prioritised and working groups formed. Each working group then started with the inventory of existing definitions, protocols/guidances, and criteria with focus on substances, application domains and techniques for Y1-Y2 in WP4 and WP5.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

Not applicable.

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

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1.9.4. Task 9.4 Training

Leader:

Participants: ANSES (FR), INRAE (FR), ONIRIS (FR), BRGM (FR), LNE (FR), UMIT (AT), Sciensano (BE), MU (CZ), VSCHT (CZ), IPA (DE), IRFM (IT), RSU (LV), NPHSL (LT), LNS (LU), STAMI (NO), NMBU (NO), ENSP (PT), UAVR (PT), JSI (SI), ULFFA (SI), NIJZ (SI), IDAEA-CSIC (ES), ISCIII (ES), FNS (ES), KI (SE), BPI (GR), GCSL (GR)

Specific objective of the task for Y1: Identifying existing training needs through interaction with WPs and a survey

Summary of the work achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022:

Considering the great number and the variable spectrum of partners involved, a self-administered online survey was developed to effectively gather information on training needs from the different PARC participants and experts, stakeholders, representatives of research institutions and members of the national and EU agencies. The content of the survey was prepared and reviewed/revised jointly following the collaborative effort of task partners, WP contact points, and national hub coordinators (Nov 2022), while the formatting, distribution, and collection were discussed and aligned with WP2 and WP3 (Oct/Nov 2022). Data collected via this survey, which were distributed during the beginning of 2023, will be analysed/compiled in an official report to be disseminated by M12, and will feed to the subsequent activities of Task 9.4, namely the mapping of existing training networks/opportunities, and planning of training activities.

List of deliverables, additional deliverables and milestones to be achieved during the period from 1 May 2022 to 30 April 2023:

No.	Title	Leader	Due date	Actual Delivery date	Explanation related to delays
D9.3	Report on Training events Y1	INSA	30/04/2023 (M12)	Ongoing	No significant delay expected

Problems encountered during the implementation of the work planned during the period from 1 May 2022 to 31 December 2022, if any:

No problem encountered.

2. Overview manuscripts/publication

- Abdellatif, M., T. Eisenberg, A. M. Heberle, K. Thedieck, G. Kroemer, and S. Sedej. "Cardiac Pi3k P110a Attenuation Delays Aging and Extends Lifespan." *Cell Stress* 6, no. 8 (2022): 72-75. doi:10.15698/cst2022.08.270.
- Askham, C., V. H. Pauna, A. M. Boulay, P. Fantke, O. Jolliet, J. Lavoie, A. M. Booth, *et al.* "Generating Environmental Sampling and Testing Data for Micro- and Nanoplastics for Use in Life Cycle Impact Assessment." *Science of the Total Environment* 859 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.160038.
- Bajard, L., O. Adamovsky, K. Audouze, K. Baken, R. Barouki, J. B. Beltman, A. Beronius, *et al.* "Application of Aops to Assist Regulatory Assessment of Chemical Risks – Case Studies, Needs and Recommendations." *Environmental Research* 217 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.envres.2022.114650.
- Blum, J., S. Masjosthusmann, K. Bartmann, F. Bendt, X. Dolde, A. Dönmez, N. Förster, *et al.* "Establishment of a Human Cell-Based in Vitro Battery to Assess Developmental Neurotoxicity Hazard of Chemicals." *Chemosphere* 311 (2023). doi:10.1016/j.chemosphere.2022.137035.
- Carney Almroth, B., S. E. Cornell, M. L. Diamond, C. A. de Wit, P. Fantke, and Z. Wang. "Understanding and Addressing the Planetary Crisis of Chemicals and Plastics." *One Earth* 5, no. 10 (2022): 1070-74. doi:10.1016/j.oneear.2022.09.012.
- Fantke, P., Y. Bruinen de Bruin, U. Schlüter, A. Connolly, J. Bessems, S. Kephelopoulos, M. Zare Jeddi, *et al.* "The European Exposure Science Strategy 2020–2030." *Environment International* 170 (2022). doi:10.1016/j.envint.2022.107555.
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